

Determinants of cryptocurrency and decentralized finance adoption - A configurational exploration

Linh Thi My Nguyen^{*}, Phong Thanh Nguyen

The Business School, RMIT University, Saigon South Campus, Viet Nam

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Configurational analysis
FsQCA
Cryptocurrency
Decentralized finance
Technology adoption
Determinants

ABSTRACT

Over the past three decades, scholars have studied technology adoption and its determinants in many contexts. Nevertheless, this literature has remained silent in understanding the complex interdependency among these determinants and how such interdependency determines technology adoption. In this paper, we build on previous research to focus on the technological, social, economic, cultural, and political determinants of technology adoption. Using the Fuzzy-set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (FsQCA) with samples of 101 and 43 countries, we perform a configurational analysis to explore the interdependency among these five categories of factors and their causal effect on the adoption of cryptocurrency and decentralized finance (DeFi). We obtain various causal combinations of the technological, social, economic, cultural, and political factors that are associated with a high level of cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption. In addition, our analysis highlights the key role of the social, economic, and cultural factors in influencing both crypto and DeFi adoption. Technological and political factors, nevertheless, play a less important role in driving blockchain adoption. We also find intriguing differences between cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption. Our results both support and challenge existing findings in the technology adoption literature and offer theoretical implications for future research.

1. Introduction

Technology adoption (TA) refers to the process by which individuals or organizations adopt new and improved technology (e.g., platform-based, information and/or financial technology) in their work (Calantone et al., 2006; Huarng and Yu, 2022; Venkatesh and Davis, 2000; Yadegari et al., 2022). With a long tradition of TA research, we have already established that TA plays a critical role in improving the productivity and welfare of various stakeholders (e.g., individuals, firms, and/or regions) in economic systems (Besley and Case, 1993; Foster and Rosenzweig, 2010). For instance, TA is associated with such economic outcomes as reducing food insecurity and poverty (e.g., Besley and Case, 1993; Takahashi et al., 2020) and enhancing the productivity and wage of workers (e.g., Acemoglu et al., 2007; Doss, 2006; Foster and Rosenzweig, 2010). In addition, we know from previous research that numerous TA determinants, including economic development (e.g., Dekimpe et al., 2000), cultural values (e.g., Kumar et al., 2021; Qu et al., 2011), social connectedness (e.g., Leister et al., 2022), technology (e.g., Huarng and Yu, 2022), and political factors (e.g., Cervellati et al., 2018; Hooks et al., 2022; Smidt and Jokonya, 2022). Overall, this prior

research has offered firms and policymakers important implications in enhancing TA at multiple levels (i.e., individual, firm, country) and thereby responded to technological change and development. In this paper, we focus on examining the country-level technology adoption by addressing the need for more TA research at this level (Borgi and Tawiah, 2022; Takeddine and Sun, 2015).

Although we are aware of the wide range of factors that are associated with technology adoption, this literature is limited in understanding the complex *interdependency* among these factors and how such interdependency influences the country-level TA (see for an exception Huarng and Yu, 2022). This limitation means that while research has indicated that a country's economic development, social factors, cultural values, technology, or political factors are separately associated with its TA, we are left uncertain if these five sets of factors come together such that they constitute different configurations that represent different pathways to predict the country's level of technology adoption. One possible relevant work is Huarng and Yu's (2022) configurational analysis that explores how the interdependency among technology, economic development, innovation, and entrepreneurship factors is associated with a country's fintech adoption. The authors find that

^{*} Corresponding author at: RMIT University – Saigon South Campus, 702 Nguyen Van Linh District 7, Ho Chi Minh City, Viet Nam.

E-mail address: linh.nguyenthimy2@rmit.edu.vn (L.T.M. Nguyen).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2024.123244>

Received 28 November 2022; Received in revised form 13 December 2023; Accepted 19 January 2024

Available online 6 February 2024

0040-1625/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Inc. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

countries with combinations of high values in the four variables tend to have high fintech adoption. Nevertheless, Huanrg and Yu's (2022) analysis does not take into account factors such as cultural differences and social connectedness that have been identified as critical determinants of TA (see Leister et al., 2022; Steers et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2021). Furthermore, while acknowledging previous research, we argue that examining the link between each individual factor and country-level TA could raise concern about whether the research findings can be generalized across countries because this approach has ignored the possible influence of the contextual differences (van Oorschot et al., 2018). For instance, although we know from prior studies that technology readiness is associated with a country's TA (e.g., Jafari-Sadeghi et al., 2021), we might not be confident that such an association is consistent across countries given that those countries might have different in cultural values (e.g., uncertainty avoidance) or political views. In sum, in this paper, we extend this TA literature by conducting a configurational analysis of the country-level adoption of blockchain technology including cryptocurrency and decentralized finance (DeFi) adoption and how such adoption is determined by different combinations of the economic, technological, cultural, social, and political factors.

There is an increasing number of studies that examine blockchain technology adoption because scholars have recognized its potential applications and benefits in our economic and social systems (e.g., Aslam et al., 2021; Bhimani et al., 2022; Ghode et al., 2020; Iansiti and Lakhani, 2017; Jovanovic et al., 2022; Köhler et al., 2022; Sarker and Datta, 2022; Toufaily et al., 2021). According to Beck et al. (2018, pp. 1020-1021), blockchain technology refers to "a decentralized, transactional database technology that facilitates validated, tamper-resistant transactions that are consistent across a large number of network participants called nodes". Blockchain technology reduces transaction costs, empowers decentralized governance, and generates distributed trust, serving as platforms for novel business applications such as decentralized finance (i.e., DeFi) and digital assets such as blockchain tokens or cryptocurrencies (e.g., bitcoin, ether, litecoin) (Allen et al., 2020; Chen, 2018; Zetzsche et al., 2020). In this blockchain context, the adoption of DeFi and cryptocurrencies creates the potentials to enhance financial inclusion whereby anyone with a smartphone and Internet connection can have access to financial services (Chen and Bellavitis, 2020; Schuetz and Venkatesh, 2020; Zetzsche et al., 2020). Such adoption would greatly benefit society noting the figures from The World Bank that there are 1.7 billion adults globally who do not have a bank account, yet around two-thirds of these adults have a mobile phone giving them access to financial services (see Felsenthal and Hahn, 2018).

It is important to study country-level blockchain adoption and its determinants due to the following two main reasons. First, research and empirical reports have indicated different levels of blockchain adoption across countries (e.g., Bhimani et al., 2022; Buchholz, 2021; Chainalysis, 2021), raising the question of what country-level factors are associated with such differences in the adoption. Second, examining blockchain adoption provides opportunities to strengthen the existing nomological network of technology adoption and its antecedents in the context of blockchain technology. As such, we can conclude whether this emerging context adds on to or challenges what we already know in TA literature (see a review from Qin et al., 2022; van Oorschot et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2021).

In this paper, we focus on the adoption of DeFi and cryptocurrencies as two indicators of country-level blockchain adoption. We build on and extend the previous research to examine five categories of technology adoption predictors, namely, *economic* (e.g., GDP per capita, inflation rate (CPI), and financial development), *technological* (e.g., network readiness), *cultural* (e.g., uncertainty avoidance, future orientation), *social* (e.g., social connectedness, human development index, population), and *political category* (e.g., democracy index) and identify different combinations of these factors that are associated with a high (or low) level of blockchain adoption. To achieve this objective, we analyze data

from 101 and 43 countries via the Fuzzy-set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (FsQCA) (Ragin, 2000, 2008a; Ragin, 2014), which allows us to explore the causal combinations of factors that lead to an outcome (i.e., blockchain adoption in a country) (Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle, 2021). The FsQCA method allows theory elaboration whereby causal factors are obtained from prior studies and then combined into one analysis to explore their complex interdependency (Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle, 2021; Misangyi et al., 2016).

With this focus, we contribute to the TA literature in at least five important ways. First, we reveal the combinations of the five sets of country-level factors leading to high cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption. While acknowledging recent studies that seek to explain cryptocurrency adoption (e.g., Alnasa'a et al., 2022; Auer et al., 2022; Bhimani et al., 2022; Jonker, 2019; Saiedi et al., 2021), our study is different in the sense that using fsQCA allows us to understand and extend theoretical insights of how the complex interdependency among the five categories of factors leads to higher adoption of cryptocurrency and DeFi. Second, as we examine the five categories of factors together, our study reveals the relative importance of these factors in driving blockchain adoption across countries. This informs policymakers of the most important areas among the economic, technological, cultural, social, and political categories that they should prioritize in enabling the country's blockchain adoption. Third, our analysis is among the few studies to examine the role of social connectedness on TA (see Leister et al., 2022; Wu and Pretty, 2004). We add to the TA literature by recognizing that, combined with other factors, the presence or absence of social network effects can enable blockchain adoption in a country. Fourth, we respond to the call for examining the role of cultural differences in explaining TA-related phenomena, identified from Xu et al.'s (2021) bibliometric analysis of technology adoption literature. Finally, our study not only offers a quantitative analysis of the combinations/configurations of the driving factors of blockchain TA but also provides a qualitative discussion of cases (i.e., countries) that fit into each configuration. As such, we provide clear implications and directions for policymakers and organizations in driving financial inclusion across the globe.

2. Literature review and theoretical background

2.1. Cryptocurrency and decentralized finance (DeFi) adoption

Blockchain technology is a distributed digital ledger that enables a single version of truth among network participants without relying on a central authority such as banks (Beck et al., 2018; Schuetz and Venkatesh, 2020). A typical blockchain, such as Bitcoin, contains records or blocks of information that are time-stamped and cryptographically linked together and are shared among network participants (Andoni et al., 2019). Any alternation of information in a block will result in the change of this block identification number making all subsequent blocks recreated (Schar and Aleksander, 2020). Blockchain technology utilizes asymmetric cryptography that prevents the ledger's information and messages from being tampered with (Hashemi Joo et al., 2020). Specifically, each blockchain user owns a pair of private and public keys. According to Zheng et al. (2017), the private key, which is kept confidential by the owner, allows the owner to sign the transaction or create new (transaction) information. This user's public key then allows other network participants to verify the content and authentication of this new information before adding it to the existing blockchain. Moreover, blockchain technology utilizes consensus mechanisms (e.g., proof-of-work, proof-of-stake), coupled with crypto-economic incentives (see Bitcoin for an example, Nakamoto, 2008) that motivate network participants (e.g., miners or validators) to continually verify the blockchain information and thereby contribute to ensuring the security of the blockchain. These features enable network participants to maintain a distributed, decentralized, transparent, and secured version of the blockchain without the need for a central authority.

With these core characteristics, blockchain technology offers novel

financial applications such as cryptocurrencies and decentralized finance. Cryptocurrency is among the first applications or adoptions of blockchain technology that has gained much attention from scholars, government, and industry (Carson et al., 2018; Hashemi Joo et al., 2020; Sousa et al., 2022). Urquhart and Lucey (2022) observe that nearly 20,000 cryptocurrencies (e.g., bitcoin, ether, etc.) are in circulation with a total market capitalization around 2 trillion USD. According to Corbet et al. (2019, p. 182), cryptocurrencies refer to “peer-to-peer electronic cash systems which allow online payments to be sent directly from one party to another without going through a financial institution”. Blockchain technology also brings forward the (new) concept of decentralized finance (DeFi). According to Piñeiro-Chousa et al. (2022), DeFi is “a novel disruptive process that promotes the use of blockchain technology for creating and issuing all kinds of financial products and services” (p. 1). DeFi typically involves the use of 1) smart contracts whereby agreements between parties are executed by programming codes (Buterin, 2014; Schär, 2021), 2) trustless and decentralized governance structures that reduce the need for intermediaries (Chen and Bellavitis, 2020), and 3) public blockchains that are accessible to everyone (i.e., public) (Beck et al., 2018), to develop a finance system that enables “complex financial products and transactions in a trustless and borderless manner” (Meyer et al., 2021, p. 1). Various business models have been identified from this concept of decentralized finance, such as decentralized payment services, exchange protocols, fundraising (e.g., ICOs), and lending platforms (Chen and Bellavitis, 2020; Piñeiro-Chousa et al., 2022; Piñeiro-Chousa et al., 2023; Schär, 2021).

There is a growing consensus that the adoption of cryptocurrency and DeFi plays a critical role in enhancing financial inclusion (Chen and Bellavitis, 2020; Lichtfous et al., 2018; Schuetz and Venkatesh, 2020). We define financial inclusion as the extent to which people have access to “appropriate, low cost, fair and safe financial products and services from main-stream service providers” (Varghese and Viswanathan, 2018, p. 2). Addressing financial exclusion (or enhancing financial inclusion) is particularly important given the fact that there are 1.7 billion adults globally who remain unbanked (Felsenthal and Hahn, 2018) and more than 200 million SMEs having difficulties in accessing the traditional banking system (Lichtfous et al., 2018). Many people, especially in developing countries, have been financially excluded because of the limited geographical access to financial institutions, relatively high fees for payment services or opening an account, and lack of financial products that meet their needs, eligibility, and circumstances (Lichtfous et al., 2018; Varghese and Viswanathan, 2018).

We argue that blockchain technology, and more specifically cryptocurrency and DeFi, offer viable solutions for addressing these financial exclusion issues. With the use of consensus mechanisms like proof-of-work and proof-of-stake, the adoption of cryptocurrency and DeFi largely reduces the transaction costs related to the involvement of third-party intermediaries (Lichtfous et al., 2018; Schuetz and Venkatesh, 2020). Given that most unbanked individuals (i.e., two-third) own a mobile phone (Felsenthal and Hahn, 2018), a blockchain-based financial solution can also address the aforementioned issue of geographical access to financial institutions because such a solution can be delivered through mobile applications (Schuetz and Venkatesh, 2020). In addition, decentralized finance, with the support of blockchain technology, enables a high level of transparency and trust in the financial system (Chen and Bellavitis, 2020), giving rise to new financial products and services (e.g., informal and peer-to-peer transactions) that better suit the needs and circumstances of financially excluded individuals (Schuetz and Venkatesh, 2020).

Previous research has identified that technology and blockchain adoption (e.g., cryptocurrency and DeFi) is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. Particularly, scholars have argued that one can explain such adoption via social, economic, technological, political, and cultural standpoints (e.g., Ao et al., 2023; Bhimani et al., 2022; Jalan et al., 2023; Langenohl, 2022; Leister et al., 2022; Piñeiro-Chousa et al., 2023). For instance, Piñeiro-Chousa et al. (2023) obtain evidence for the impacts of

tweets information and social indicators on DeFi adoption. Jalan et al. (2023) observe that cryptocurrency adoption is driven by societal trust and national cultural values. Other scholars have adopted social networks (e.g., Ao et al., 2023) and political, legal, and regulatory perspectives (e.g., Bhimani et al., 2022; Langenohl, 2022) in discussing blockchain adoption and its implications. Moreover, we acknowledge previous research like that of Bhimani et al. (2022) that investigates the impact of multiple national developmental indicators (e.g., human development index, network readiness, democracy, etc.) on the country-level adoption of cryptocurrency across 137 countries. However, their study, though important in revealing the contributing factors of cryptocurrency adoption, is limited in capturing the interdependency among these developmental indicators and how such interdependency explains the adoption. In this paper, we seek to address this limitation by adopting a configurational analysis that examines the complex interdependent relationships among the five categories of social, economic, political, technological, and cultural variables and their combined impact on the adoption of cryptocurrency and DeFi. In the following section, we discuss these variables in detail.

2.2. Influence factors of cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption

2.2.1. Social factors

Prior studies have found consistent evidence of the relationship between various social factors and technology adoption (TA) in a country. Although research in blockchain technology adoption is relatively new, we review relevant TA literature and identify three relevant social factors that can drive a country’s blockchain adoption, including social connectedness, human development, and population.

Social connectedness. Social learning can foster technology adoption by accumulating more relevant knowledge about the technology (Genius et al., 2014). Genius and colleagues find social connection with their peers is a significant channel through which farmers accumulate knowledge about the adoption of modern technology. Studying social networks and new agricultural technology adoption from 200 different villages, Beaman et al. (2021) also show that compared to people without any direct connections with the “trained seeds”, those that are close to them tend to adopt the new technology more. Their study highlights the importance of multiple connections (rather than one) before one becomes educated about the new technology and then makes an adoption decision. Similarly, in a recent study, Leister et al. (2022) find people with high social connectedness are more likely to adopt new technology. However, importantly, Higgins (2019) notes that to enhance the adoption of new technology, social learning needs to be about the benefits of that technology. As a result, if the new technology’s performance is not clear to people or the information about it is incomplete, the social learning process can be weaker (Molleman et al., 2014; Munshi, 2004), which in turn may hinder the technology adoption.

Human development. “Adoption decision-making is a human capital intensive activity” (Wozniak, 1987, p. 101). Human capital is also considered as among the main factors that determine the technology development in a country (Gorlacheva et al., 2019). According to the human capital theory (Becker, 1964), human capital is an important factor driving entrepreneurs’ decisions, including technology adoption (Ganotakis et al., 2021). Wozniak (1987) also finds that education increases the chance of new technology early adoption by lowering uncertainty and the costs of adoption. New technology may demand more advanced knowledge and skills, thus a high level of human development can enhance the adoption of new technology.

Population. Prior literature shows that a large population can either enhance or hinder technology adoption. Technology adoption can be challenging in a country with a high population due to administration and finance-related constraints (Stier, 2017). However, a high population can also foster technology adoption via economies of scale and network effect (Rogers et al., 2014). Indeed, Desmet and Parente (2014)

show that in economies with a large population, new technology is likely to be adopted. Similarly, Dekimpe et al. (2000) find that countries with concentrated populations tend to adopt technology (i.e., cellular telephone) earlier.

2.2.2. Economic factors

In their study, Dekimpe et al. (2000) investigate why some nations adopt new technology earlier than others through three groups of determinants: demographic, economic/political, and social factors. They find that countries with high economic development tend to adopt the technology sooner. Building on prior research, we have identified three main economic factors, including income level, inflation, and financial development, that are relevant to cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption.

Income level (GDP per capita). People with a lower income level tend to focus more on their basic needs than adopting new technology, while people with a higher income level have more resources to support the adoption (Bhimani et al., 2022). GDP per capita has been found to be a significant influencing factor in the adoption of various types of technology (Comin and Hobijn, 2004; Kiiski and Pohjola, 2002; Saiedi et al., 2021). For example, Comin and Hobijn (2004) study cross-country technology adoption and find a positive link between GDP per capita and technology adoption in a country. Similarly, Saiedi et al. (2021) investigate factors affecting cryptocurrency infrastructure adoption globally and show that GDP per capita is positively linked with adoption.

Inflation. Most countries do not recognize bitcoin or cryptocurrency as currency, rather, they are mainly considered as a speculative asset (Pagnotta, 2022; Yermack, 2015). Cryptocurrency, especially Bitcoin with its fixed supply, has been documented as a potential hedging asset for inflation (Choi and Shin, 2022; Nakamoto, 2008). Studies also show that bitcoin can be a safe haven in some countries (e.g., Venezuela) when facing with very high inflation (i.e., hyperinflation) (Kliber et al., 2019). When there is high inflation which weakens the country's fiat currency, its people tend to adopt more cryptocurrency as a way to protect their wealth and/or earn their living. Indeed, Saiedi et al. (2021) find more cryptocurrency infrastructure adoption in countries that experience inflation crises.

Financial development. Financial development has been found to foster economic growth through the efficient allocation of resources and reduced financial constraints (Comin and Nanda, 2019). Technology adoption is considered as a main channel to boost productivity growth which in turn enhances economic growth (Aghion and Howitt, 1992; Comin and Hobijn, 2010). Utilizing a rich dataset in 17 countries over 130 years, Comin and Nanda (2019) show that financial development speeds up technology diffusion in a country. However, the authors also note that this positive impact is only significant in the early stages of commercializing new technology. Blockchain technology can be applied in a variety of areas, and the financial industry is among the most popular ones (e.g., fintech, insurance, payments, peer-to-peer lending, and investment). Despite employing the new blockchain technology with unique features (such as decentralization), these applications are still built on relevant concepts in the current financial system. Thus, strong financial development can accelerate the adoption of this new technology. However, there are a number of studies that report conflicting findings about the impact of financial development and cryptocurrency adoption. For example, Alnasaa et al. (2022) conduct a multi-country study on the correlation between crypto asset usage and various explanatory factors and document a negative link between financial development (proxied by the number of commercial bank branches per 100,000 adults) and crypto usage. Likewise, Feyen et al. (2022) show that financial development measured by domestic credit and financial account ownership is not a significant factor explaining crypto-asset activity in a country.

2.2.3. Political factor

Democracy. Research has also offered insights into the relevance of

political factors in explaining a country's level of technology adoption (e.g., Corrales and Westhoff, 2006; Gao et al., 2017; Milner, 2006). According to Milner (2006), country-level technology (Internet) adoption has been driven "neither by technological forces nor by economic ones alone. Rather, political factors, especially domestic institutions, exert a powerful influence" (p. 178). The author argue that political institutions play critical roles in this regard as they influence the ways through which those who gain benefit or experience potential loss from the new technology can translate "their preferences into influence" (p. 178). In this paper, we focus on the level of democracy which refers to the extent to which a country pays attention to respecting and ensuring individual freedoms and rights (Gao et al., 2017). Democracy is one of the three main aspects of institutional quality that are argued to influence economic decision-making (La Porta et al., 1999). Democracy impacts the lobbying costs and regulatory capture regarding the new technology, which in turn can enhance the technology adoption (Comin and Hobijn, 2004; Comin and Hobijn, 2009; Galang, 2012). Compared to autocratic countries, democratic countries tend to adopt technology (i.e., internet) faster (Milner, 2006). Notably, Corrales and Westhoff (2006) find that higher-income authoritarian regimes tend to less discourage Internet adoption than lower-income authoritarian regimes, suggesting the combined effects of political and economic factors on technology adoption.

2.2.4. Technological factor

Network readiness. Blockchain is a network-based technology (Toufaily et al., 2021), thus the readiness of a country's network infrastructure can drive the technology adoption in that country. The Network Readiness Index by the Portulans Institute measures "the ability of the country to exploit the advantages offered by information communication and technology" (Bhimani et al., 2022, p. 4) comprising of four fundamental components: technology, governance, people, and impact. The index is considered a benchmark for evaluating the degree of technology adoption globally (Dutta and Lanvin, 2019). Prior literature also shows supporting evidence for the positive link between network readiness and cryptocurrency adoption (see Bhimani et al., 2022).

2.2.5. Cultural factors

Uncertainty avoidance. Uncertainty avoidance refers to "the extent to which a society, organizations, or groups relies on social norms, rules, and procedures to alleviate the unpredictability of future events" (Dorfman et al., 2012, p. 516). This national cultural value has been identified as an important determinant of new technology adoption (e.g., Hwang, 2005; Kumar et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2013; Takeddine and Sun, 2015) or serves as a moderator or contextual condition of the link between technology adoption and its determinants (e.g., Kim and Kim, 2021; Yoon, 2009). For instance, Qu et al. (2011) obtain supporting evidence that uncertainty avoidance is positively associated with open-source software (OSS) adoption by firms within the country. In addition, Kim and Kim (2021) observe in their study that high uncertainty avoidance weakens the relationship between user satisfaction and intention to accept robot journalism.

Future orientation. Future orientation refers to "the extent to which individuals engage in future-oriented behaviors such as delaying gratification, planning, and investing in the future" (Dorfman et al., 2012, p. 516). A future-oriented culture encourages risk-taking and experimentation as well as enables its members to adopt new technology or practices that provide them with future or long-term benefits (Bortolotti et al., 2015; Naor et al., 2010; Zhao et al., 2014). For instance, Zhao and colleagues find that a country's high level of future orientation is associated with its citizens' adoption of e-government which is key to sustainable development. In addition, the authors document the moderating role of economic development such that the association between future orientation and the adoption is stronger for countries with high economic development. Overall, given the potential roles of

cryptocurrency and DeFi in addressing issues about financial inclusion, we argue that future orientation is an important determinant of these two blockchain adoption indexes.

3. Method

3.1. Data and sample

We employ a global cross-sectional dataset of cryptocurrency adoption and DeFi adoption of 154 countries in 2021 from Chainalysis – a blockchain data platform that provides blockchain data for government agencies, financial institutions, and businesses in over 70 countries, including Barclays, Commonwealth bank, and the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime.¹ We also collect the 2021 data of relevant social, economic, political, technological, and cultural factors from various reliable sources (except for financial development index data retrieved from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) in 2020 and cultural factors retrieved from the GLOBE project - phase 2² in 2006 due to limited data availability) (Table 2), and then map them with the cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption dataset. After deleting countries with insufficient data for analysis, our final sample consists of 101 countries without cultural factors and 43 countries with cultural factors. The following section will discuss our measures and data sources in detail.

3.2. Measures

3.2.1. Cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption indices

Table 2 summarizes our main variables' measurements. Particularly, we employ the global crypto and DeFi adoption indices from Chainalysis to reflect a country's blockchain technology adoption. In particular, Chainalysis ranks 154 countries based on their people's crypto/defi activity.³ The crypto adoption index consists of three dimensions: the value of on-chain cryptocurrency received, the value of on-chain retail value transferred, and peer-to-peer exchange trade volume, all weighted by purchasing power parity (PPP) per capita (and by the number of internet users for the third dimension). Similarly, the DeFi adoption index is constructed based on three components: the value of on-chain cryptocurrency received by DeFi platforms weighted by PPP per capita, the value of retail transactions received by DeFi platforms, and individual deposits to DeFi platforms. Table 1 shows the top 20 countries that have the highest crypto adoption and DeFi adoption index score. According to Chainalysis, the global adoption of cryptocurrency at the end of Q2/2021 has increased by more than 2300 % compared to that of Q3/2019 and 881 % to that of the year 2020.

3.2.2. Social factors

Social factors include the social connectedness index (Bailey et al., 2018), human development index (Bhimani et al., 2022), and population (Saiedi et al., 2021). First, we employ the social connectedness index (SCI) constructed by Bailey et al. (2018) to measure the (online) social links between countries. Bailey and colleagues first map the location of users with respect to their country's location, and calculate the number of Facebook friendship links in every country-pair (for example, between the U.S. and Australia). They then construct the SCI index as the "normalized total number of friendship links for each geographic pair" (p. 261). The SCI data is available from the Humanitarian Data Exchange. We then sum all the SCI indices of a country (with other countries and itself) to proxy for the country overall social connectedness. Second, we use the human development index (HDI) by

Table 1

The 2021 cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption top 20 countries.

Country	Crypto adoption index score	Country	DeFi adoption index score
Vietnam	1.00	United States	1.00
India	0.37	Vietnam	0.82
Pakistan	0.36	Thailand	0.68
Ukraine	0.29	China	0.62
Kenya	0.28	United Kingdom	0.60
Nigeria	0.26	India	0.59
Venezuela	0.25	Netherlands	0.55
United States	0.22	Canada	0.52
Togo	0.19	Ukraine	0.49
Argentina	0.19	Poland	0.46
Colombia	0.19	France	0.46
Thailand	0.17	Australia	0.41
China	0.16	Turkey	0.40
Brazil	0.16	Switzerland	0.38
Philippines	0.16	Russia	0.36
South Africa	0.14	Argentina	0.34
Ghana	0.14	Brazil	0.32
Russia	0.14	Portugal	0.31
Tanzania	0.13	Hongkong	0.30
Afghanistan	0.13	Togo	0.30

^a <https://www.chainalysis.com/>.

Source: data are from Chainalysis.com.^a

United Nations.⁴ The HDI is a composite measure calculated as the geometric mean of the three components' normalized indices including: long and healthy life, knowledge, and a decent standard of living. Third, following prior research (Saiedi et al., 2021), we also include the country's population data downloaded from World Bank (World Development Indicators). We then take the natural logarithm of the population.

3.2.3. Economic factors

We employ the following economic variables in our analysis: GDP per capita (PPP), inflation, and Financial Development Index (FDI) (Auer et al., 2022; Bhimani et al., 2022; Saiedi et al., 2021). We collect GDP per capital and inflation (consumer price index- CPI) data from World Bank (World Development Indicators). The Financial Development Index (FDI) measures the development of financial systems of various countries around the world (Sviryzdenka, 2016). The FDI comprises of two components, including financial institutions and financial markets, each of which is measured under three dimensions: depth, access, and efficiency. We download FDI data from International Monetary Fund (IMF). However, the 2021 FDI data is not available, so we use the 2020 FDI index instead.

3.2.4. Political factor

We employ the Global Democracy Index retrieved from the Economic Intelligent Unit (EIU) to proxy for the democracy level in a country (Bhimani et al., 2022). The democracy index is measured on a 0 to 10 scale as an average of its five components: "electoral process and pluralism, civil liberties, the functioning of government, political participation, and political culture" which are measured by 60 indicators or questionnaire items. According to the EIU, compared to existing democracy measures, their global democracy index is argued to be a "thicker, more inclusive, and wider" measure. Another distinct feature of the global democracy index by the EIU is that it is assessed by both experts and the public (from public-opinion surveys such as the World Values Survey).

¹ <https://www.chainalysis.com/>.

² <https://globeproject.com/data/GLOBE-Dimensions-Definitions-and-Scale-Items.pdf>.

³ <https://blog.chainalysis.com/reports/2021-global-crypto-adoption-index/>; <https://blog.chainalysis.com/reports/2021-global-defi-adoption-index/>.

⁴ <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index/#/indicies/HDI>.

Table 2
Variable description.

Variable	Description	Data source
Cryptocurrency adoption/DeFi adoption	Cryptocurrency/DeFi adoption in a country	Chainalysis https://www.chainalysis.com/
Social factors		
Social connectedness index (SCI)	SCI is measured through the number of Facebook friendship links in every country-pair.	The Humanitarian Data Exchange https://data.humdata.org/dataset/social-connectedness-index
Human development index (HDI)	HDI is a composite measure calculated as the geometric mean of the three components' normalized indices including: long and healthy life, knowledge, and a decent standard of living.	United Nations: https://hdr.undp.org/
Population	Total population of a country (logarithm)	World Bank Indicator: https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL
Economic factors		
Income level	GDP per capital, PPP	World Bank Indicator: https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.PP.CD
Inflation	Consumer price index (CPI).	World Bank Indicator: https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG
Financial development index (FDI)	FDI measures the development of financial systems of various countries around the world	International Monetary Fund: https://data.imf.org/?sk=F8032E80-B36C-43B1-AC26-493C5B1CD33B&slid=1481126573525
Political factor		
Democracy	The democracy index is measured on a 0 to 10 scale as an average of its five components: 'electoral process and pluralism, civil liberties, the functioning of government, political participation, and political culture'	Economic Intelligence Unit: https://www.eiu.com/n/
Technological factor		
Network readiness index (NRI)	NRI refers to "the ability of the country to exploit the advantages offered by information communication and technology" (Bhimani et al., 2022, p. 4) measured by four fundamental dimensions including technology, governance, people, and impact.	Portulans Institute: https://networkreadinessindex.org/
Cultural factors		
Uncertainty avoidance (social practices)	Uncertainty avoidance refers to "the extent to which a society, organization, or group relies on social norms, rules, and procedures to alleviate unpredictability of future events" (Dorfman et al., 2012, p. 516).	The Global Leadership & Organizational Behavior Effectiveness (GLOBE) project – Phase 2 (Beta form)
Future oriented (social practices)	Future orientation is defined as "the extent to which individuals engage in future-oriented behaviors such as delaying gratification, planning, and investing in the future" (Dorfman et al., 2012, p. 516)	The Global Leadership & Organizational Behavior Effectiveness (GLOBE) project – Phase 2 (beta form)

Note. All data are collected for the year 2021, except for the Financial Development Index (FDI) (2020) and Uncertainty avoidance and Future orientation survey data (2006).

3.2.5. Technological factor

We employ the Network Readiness Index (NRI) which measures "the ability of the country to exploit the advantages offered by information communication and technology" (Bhimani et al., 2022, p. 4) as a technological factor that can influence blockchain technology adoption of that country. The index created by the Portulans Institute is a multi-dimensional construct measured by three levels: the first level/pillar comprises of four fundamental dimensions including technology, governance, people, and impact; the second level consists of the sub-pillars of the four dimensions; and the last level comprises of individual indicators of the first and second level dimensions or pillars.⁵ In particular, the technology dimension refers to the level of technology in a country (access, content, and future technologies). The governance dimension measures the extent to which firms and individuals in a country are safe in the network economy (trust, regulation, inclusion). The people dimension measures whether a country's individuals, businesses, and governments have access, resources, and necessary skills to use the technology. The last dimension, impact, captures the impact of technology on the economy, quality of life, and sustainable development goals.

3.2.6. Cultural factors

We use two relevant cultural factors that are argued to be potential drivers of cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption in a country: uncertainty avoidance and future orientation. We collect data of the two societal culture variables from the Global Leadership & Organizational Behavior Effectiveness (GLOBE) project (Dorfman et al., 2012). The GLOBE project is a global research project involving more than 200 scholars around the world with an aim to study leadership, organizational behavior as well as cultural dimensions across 62 countries (Dorfman et al., 2012; Kabasakal et al., 2012). Uncertainty avoidance refers to "the extent to which a society, organization, or group relies on social norms, rules, and procedures to alleviate unpredictability of future events" and future orientation is defined as "the extent to which individuals engage in future-oriented behaviors such as delaying gratification, planning, and investing in the future" (Dorfman et al., 2012, p. 516). The GLOBE research team develops scales to ask respondents about their beliefs on these cultural dimensions in their society/country. Responses are then aggregated into the aggregated scores for each factor. There are two sets of questions to measure social practices (as is) and values (should be). We employ the aggregated data of uncertainty avoidance and future orientation social practices (i.e., actual practices) in our study. Sample items include "In this society, orderliness and consistency are stressed, even at the expense of experimentation and innovation (strongly agree: 1; strongly disagree: 7)", "In this society, most people lead highly structured lives with few unexpected events (strongly agree: 1; strongly disagree: 7)" (uncertainty avoidance), "The way to be successful in this society is to (plan ahead: 1; take life events as they occur: 7)", "In this society, people place more emphasis on (solving current problems: 1; planning for the future: 7)" (future orientation)⁶

3.3. Fuzzy set qualitative comparative approach (fsQCA)

We employ the fuzzy set qualitative comparative approach (fsQCA) (Ragin, 2000, 2008a; Ragin, 2014) which allows us to identify configurations of country-level factors (combination of causal conditions) that lead to a higher cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption in a country (Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle, 2021). The fsQCA has several advantages compared to conventional analysis methods such as standard regressions: first, it combines both quantitative and qualitative methods in one analysis (Pappas and Woodside, 2021); second, it allows us to

⁵ <https://networkreadinessindex.org/>.

⁶ <https://globeproject.com/data/GLOBE-Dimensions-Definitions-and-Scale-Items.pdf>.

Table 3
Fuzzy set calibrations and descriptive statistics.

Variable/condition	Obs	Fuzzy set calibrations			Mean	SD	Min	Max
		Fully in (95 %)	Crossover (50 %)	Fully out (5 %)				
Crypto adoption index	101	0.26	0.04	0.01	0.072	0.118	0.000	1.000
DeFi adoption index	101	0.55	0.13	0.01	0.176	0.181	0.000	1.000
Social connectedness index (Ln)	101	18.030	16.057	13.794	15.948	1.263	13.078	19.050
Human development index	101	0.947	0.802	0.511	0.774	0.142	0.428	0.962
Population (Ln)	101	19.169	16.295	14.100	16.465	1.534	12.827	21.055
GDP per capita (Ln)	101	11.146	9.128	6.822	9.182	1.398	6.216	11.818
CPI	101	9.566	3.466	0.581	5.707	15.486	-2.079	154.756
Financial development	101	0.848	0.369	0.112	0.412	0.231	0.088	0.948
Democracy index	101	9.09	6.48	2.9	6.247	1.943	2.080	9.750
Network readiness index	101	80.200	52.572	30.539	54.217	15.186	24.898	82.062
Uncertainty avoidance	43	5.306	4.166	3.391	4.218	0.598	3.116	5.371
Future orientation	43	4.643	3.810	3.237	3.885	0.496	3.106	5.068

Table 4
Necessary analysis for high cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption (without cultural factors).

	Cryptocurrency adoption		DeFi adoption	
	Consistency	Coverage	Consistency	Coverage
Social connectedness	0.544	0.477	0.554	0.501
~Social connectedness	0.847	0.701	0.805	0.687
Human development	0.622	0.507	0.780	0.656
~Human development	0.718	0.639	0.534	0.490
Population	0.894	0.752	0.758	0.658
~Population	0.533	0.459	0.586	0.520
GDP per capita	0.620	0.500	0.779	0.647
~GDP per capita	0.718	0.648	0.534	0.496
Inflation	0.704	0.633	0.604	0.560
~Inflation	0.692	0.559	0.728	0.607
Financial development	0.634	0.563	0.778	0.712
~Financial development	0.673	0.551	0.538	0.453
Democracy	0.681	0.574	0.782	0.679
~Democracy	0.683	0.587	0.545	0.483
Network readiness	0.641	0.542	0.803	0.700
~Network readiness	0.690	0.591	0.526	0.464

Table 5
Necessary analysis for high cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption (with cultural factors).

	Cryptocurrency adoption		DeFi adoption	
	Consistency	Coverage	Consistency	Coverage
Social connectedness	0.493	0.441	0.561	0.537
~Social connectedness	0.850	0.750	0.744	0.700
Human development	0.552	0.459	0.734	0.652
~Human development	0.704	0.673	0.504	0.514
Population	0.910	0.802	0.770	0.723
~Population	0.448	0.402	0.504	0.483
GDP per capita	0.528	0.458	0.706	0.653
~GDP per capita	0.749	0.684	0.555	0.541
Inflation	0.696	0.661	0.651	0.661
~Inflation	0.651	0.543	0.699	0.623
Financial development	0.647	0.568	0.785	0.735
~Financial development	0.607	0.547	0.511	0.491
Democracy	0.668	0.546	0.817	0.712
~Democracy	0.614	0.598	0.507	0.528
Network readiness	0.565	0.494	0.748	0.697
~Network readiness	0.689	0.624	0.527	0.509
Uncertainty avoidance	0.632	0.588	0.687	0.683
~Uncertainty avoidance	0.682	0.580	0.611	0.554
Future orientation	0.673	0.600	0.707	0.673
~Future orientation	0.608	0.539	0.569	0.538

explore the complex interdependency among the causal factors whose combinations lead to an outcome (Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle, 2021); and third, it also reveals hidden patterns that might be difficult to identify through the standard regression analysis (Vis, 2012). The fsQCA

Table 6
Country-level factors (without cultural factors) sufficient for high cryptocurrency adoption.

Configuration	High country-level crypto adoption		
	A1	A2	A3
Social factors			
Social connectedness	⊗	⊗	⊗
Human development	⊙	●	⊙
Population	●	●	●
Economic factors			
GDP per capita	⊙	●	⊙
Inflation			●
Financial development	⊙	●	●
Political factor			
Democracy	⊙	●	●
Technological factor			
Network readiness	⊙	●	⊙
Consistency	0.869	0.844	0.970
Raw coverage	0.461	0.452	0.268
Unique coverage	0.217	0.213	0.016
Solution consistency	0.830		
Solution coverage	0.712		

Note: ●: presence of the condition, ⊗: absence of the condition, large circle: core condition, small circle: peripheral condition. N = 101 countries.

is an inductive approach that allows theory elaboration whereby causal factors are obtained from prior studies and then combined into one analysis to explore their complex interdependency (Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle, 2021; Misangyi et al., 2016).

We first calibrate fuzzy-set memberships of the variables using the fsQCA software. We follow Pappas and Woodside (2021) to use 95 %, 50 %, and 5 % as full set membership, intermediate (crossover), and full set non-membership, respectively. The 95 % calibration threshold can be applied to most types of data (Pappas and Woodside, 2021). We add 0.001 to all the calibrated variables to avoid the challenging situation where cases of the exact intermediate or crossover points are dropped from the analysis (Fiss, 2011). Table 3 shows the fuzzy set calibrations and descriptive statistics of the main variables in our study. Although cryptocurrencies have been around for a while, their wide adoption, especially DeFi adoption, has become popular recently. Cryptocurrencies are considered relatively risky, so we argue cultural values, especially those related to risk-taking and future orientation, can affect their adoption. Theoretically, according to institutional theory (Williamson, 2000), informal social norms and values can shape the behaviors of organizations and individuals. Empirical research also shows supporting evidence of the link between uncertainty avoidance and long-term orientation and the adoption of new technology (e.g., Bortolotti et al., 2015; Hwang, 2005; Kumar et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2013; Naor et al.,

Table 7
Country-level factors (with cultural factors) sufficient for high cryptocurrency adoption.

Configuration	High country-level crypto adoption							
	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8
Social factors								
Social connectedness	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗
Human development	⊙	⊙	●	●	●	●	⊙	⊙
Population	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Economic factors								
GDP per capita	⊗	⊗	●	●	⊗	●	⊗	⊗
Inflation	⊙	●	⊙	●	●	●	●	●
Financial development								
Political factor								
Democracy	⊗	⊗	●	●	⊗	●	⊗	⊗
Technological factor								
Network readiness	⊙	⊙	●	●	●	●	⊙	⊙
Cultural factors								
Uncertainty avoidance	⊗		●	●	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗
Future Orientation	⊙	●		●	⊙	⊙	⊙	
Consistency	0.924	0.967	0.927	0.898	0.916	0.939	0.874	0.871
Raw coverage	0.320	0.282	0.356	0.337	0.196	0.229	0.335	0.320
Unique coverage	0.024	0.020	0.021	0.025	0.009	0.011	0.001	0.000
Solution consistency	0.884							
Solution coverage	0.691							

Note: ●: presence of the condition, ⊗: absence of the condition, large circle: core condition, small circle: peripheral condition. N = 43 countries.

Table 8
Country-level factors (without cultural factors) sufficient for DeFi adoption.

Configuration	High country-level defi adoption		
	C1	C2	C3
Social factors			
Social connectedness		⊗	⊗
Human development	●	●	⊙
Population	⊙	●	●
Economic factors			
GDP per capita	●	●	⊙
Inflation	⊗		●
Financial development			
Political factor			
Democracy	●	●	●
Technological factor			
Network readiness	●	●	⊙
Consistency	0.847	0.929	0.938
Raw coverage	0.406	0.483	0.251
Unique coverage	0.107	0.144	0.037
Solution consistency	0.856		
Solution coverage	0.628		

Note: ●: presence of the condition, ⊗: absence of the condition, large circle: core condition, small circle: peripheral condition. N = 101 countries.

2010; Takeddine and Sun, 2015; Zhao et al., 2014). However, data on cultural values is limited and on a cross-sectional basis, thus, when we merge all the datasets, including cultural values, our sample is only 43 countries, which may affect our results' generalizability. To address such limitation, we have decided to first analyze a larger sample (without cultural values) to examine the interdependency among other important factors and their combined impact on cryptocurrency/defi adoption (101 countries). After that, we further investigate the cultural aspects and their roles (43 countries).

We follow prior studies (e.g., Greckhamer et al., 2018; Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle, 2021; Misangyi and Acharya, 2014; Pappas and Woodside, 2021) and use current best practices to conduct the fsQCA necessary and sufficient analysis. First, we conduct the necessary analysis

(“Necessary Analysis” function) to identify factors that are necessary for high cryptocurrency/DeFi adoption to occur in a country. Following prior studies (Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle, 2021; Ragin, 2008b), we use the consistency cutoff point of 0.90 for “almost always necessary” factors. Second, we conduct sufficient analysis. We use the “Truth table algorithms” in the fsQCA software with the calibrated outcomes (cryptocurrency adoption and DeFi adoption index) and causal conditions (country-level factors). We use the frequency cut-off point of two (2) for the 101-country sample and one (1) for the 43-country sample, given its small sample size (less than 60) (Capatina et al., 2018; Pappas and Woodside, 2021). With the frequency threshold of two, we are able to keep 77 % of the cases in our analysis (for the 101-country sample without the two cultural factors), which is around the threshold of 80 % suggested by (Pappas and Woodside, 2021). With the frequency threshold of one, we are able to keep 100 % of the cases for the 43-country sample with the cultural factors. After removing cases with low frequencies, we employ the thresholds of 0.8 and 0.5 for the raw consistency and PRI consistency and code one (1) for cases that satisfy the threshold requirements (leading to the outcome) (Greckhamer et al., 2018; Pappas and Woodside, 2021). Other cases are coded as zero (0) (not leading to the outcome).

We then conduct the truth table analysis to obtain the solution sets (configurations) by using “standard analyses” function. FsQCA generates three truth table analyses/solution sets including complex solution, parsimonious solution, and intermediate solution. The complex solution shows all the possible configurations of causal conditions that lead to an outcome while the parsimonious one presents only the most important ones (Pappas and Woodside, 2021). The intermediate solution is constructed based on both the complex and parsimonious solutions through a counterfactual analysis (Pappas and Woodside, 2021). We combine the parsimonious and intermediate solutions to construct the final result tables in the following section. Lastly, to offer further insights into the complex causal relationships between country-level factors and cryptocurrency/DeFi adoption, especially the asymmetric nature, we conduct all the analyses for low cryptocurrency/DeFi adoption.

Table 9
Country-level factors (with cultural factors) sufficient for DeFi adoption.

Configuration	High country-level defi adoption								
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	D9
Social factors									
Social connectedness	⊗	⊗	⊗	●	⊗	⊗	⊗	●	●
Human development	●	⊙	●	●	●	⊙	●	●	●
Population	●	●	●	⊙	●	●	●	⊙	⊙
Economic factors									
GDP per capita	●	⊙	●	●	●	⊙	⊙	●	●
Inflation	⊙	●	●	⊙	⊙	⊙	●	⊙	●
Financial development	●	⊙	●	●	●	●	⊙	●	⊙
Political factor									
Democracy	●	⊙	●	●	●	⊙	⊙	●	●
Technological factor									
Network readiness	●	⊙	●	●	●	⊙	●	●	●
Cultural factors									
Uncertainty avoidance			⊙	●	●	⊙	⊙	⊙	●
Future Orientation		●	⊙	●	●	⊙	⊙	⊙	⊙
Consistency	0.904	0.906	0.956	0.794	0.951	0.957	0.938	0.957	0.977
Raw coverage	0.397	0.248	0.267	0.345	0.334	0.223	0.188	0.233	0.173
Unique coverage	0.012	0.081	0.008	0.087	0.031	0.026	0.009	0.024	0.015
Solution consistency	0.817								
Solution coverage	0.745								

Note: ●: presence of the condition, ⊗: absence of the condition, large circle: core condition, small circle: peripheral condition. N = 43 countries.

4. Results

4.1. Necessary analysis

Tables 4 and 5 show the results of our necessary analysis for high cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption without cultural factors and with cultural factors, respectively. Our Necessary analysis shows that consistency values range from 0.448 to 0.910. Following prior studies (Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle, 2021; Ragin, 2008b), we use the consistency cutoff point of 0.90 for “almost always necessary” factors. Consequently, there is only one factor: population in the cryptocurrency adoption (with cultural factors) that has a consistency value exceeding 0.90 (0.91). Following that, the population factor is considered necessary and must be present in all configurations of the cryptocurrency adoption (with cultural factors).

4.2. A configurational exploration of country-level crypto adoption drivers

Table 6 presents the configurational results for country-level crypto adoption (without cultural factors). To save space, we include all the Truth Tables in the Appendix. Following Ragin and Fiss (2008) and Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle (2021), we use the solid circles to represent the presence/high level of the conditions/factors and the crossed-out circles for the absence/low level of the conditions/factors. We use large circles to represent the core conditions (those that appear in both intermediate and parsimonious solutions) and small circles for peripheral conditions (those that appear only in the intermediate solution). Drawing on Fiss (2011, p. 394), we consider the core elements or conditions “as those causal conditions for which the evidence indicates a strong causal relationship with the outcome of interest” and the peripheral conditions “as those for which the evidence for a causal relationship with the outcome is weaker”. As shown in Table 6, there are three configurations that are consistently sufficient for producing high crypto adoption in a country. The overall solution consistency and coverage are 0.83 and 0.712, respectively (higher than the suggested thresholds of 0.8 and 0.5) (Pappas and Woodside, 2021), suggesting that this solution leads to high levels of crypto adoption 83 % of the time and

accounts for 71.2 % of the instances of the outcome.

In all three configurations, high population (presence of the condition) and low social connectedness (absence of the condition) are the core conditions that lead to high crypto adoption in a country, implying the importance of these factors. Configuration A1 shows that the combination of the high population with the absence of social connectedness, human development, income level (GDP per capita), financial development, democracy, and network readiness leads to high crypto adoption, regardless of the inflation level. Sample countries that have such configuration include Pakistan, Nigeria, Nepal, Algeria, Bangladesh, Ecuador, Cambodia, Guatemala, Morocco, and Sri Lanka. Configuration A2 reveals quite the opposite story, that is, for high crypto adoption to occur, there should be an absence of social connectedness in a country combined with high levels of human development, population, income level, financial development, democracy, and network readiness, regardless of the level of inflation. Sample countries that have such a combination include Japan, Germany, the United States, the United Kingdom, Spain, Italy, France, Canada, Australia, Chile, Netherlands, Poland, and Malaysia. Configuration A3 shows that when there is a high level of inflation, a combination of high population, financial development, and democracy in the absence of social connectedness, human development, income level, and network readiness leads to high crypto adoption. Sample countries that have this configuration include India and South Africa.

We conduct the analysis with a smaller sample of 43 countries with cultural factors (uncertainty avoidance and future orientation). Table 7 shows eight different configurations (B1 – B8) whose overall solution consistency is 0.884 and coverage is 0.691. The values indicate that this solution leads to high levels of crypto adoption more than 88 % of the time and accounts for almost 70 % of the instances of the outcome. In almost all configurations, high population, low social connectedness, and uncertainty avoidance (presence or absence) are the central conditions. The future orientation factor is, however, a peripheral condition in a majority of the configurations. Financial development and network readiness remain peripheral conditions in all configurations. Looking more closely into the cultural factors, both the presence of the two factors in combination with all other factors except social connectedness leads to higher crypto adoption in a country (configuration B4). The core

conditions in this configuration B4 are the social factors and uncertainty avoidance, implying their crucial role in crypto adoption. Sample countries in this group include Germany, Canada, and Australia. Configurations B2 and B3 comprise of at least one cultural factor. Particularly, a combination of high future orientation, inflation, and population, in the absence of other factors leads to a high cryptocurrency adoption, regardless of the level of uncertainty avoidance of the people in that country (configuration B2). Sample countries that have this combination include Nigeria, Philippines, and Mexico. In configuration B3, regardless of the future orientation level, high uncertainty avoidance level (core factor) combined with a high level of other factors except social connectedness and inflation brings about a high level of cryptocurrency adoption. Sample countries in this group include France and the United Kingdom. Other configurations (B1, B5, B6, B7, and B8) indicate the absence of either one or both cultural factors. For example, configuration B1 (Morocco and Thailand) and configuration B7 (Colombia) only include the presence of high population while other factors are absent (except financial development in configuration B1 and inflation in configuration B7 can be either absent or present). Configuration B5 (e.g., Poland) shows that in the absence of both cultural factors, social connectedness, income level, financial development, and democracy, the combinations of high levels of human development, population, inflation, and network readiness lead to a high crypto adoption level. Configuration B6 (e.g., Spain), on the other hand, includes the absence of cultural factors and social connectedness and the presence of all other factors. Overall, Table 7 highlights the relative importance of social factors and uncertainty avoidance compared with other factors in contributing to a high cryptocurrency adoption in a country. We can see these factors are central factors in the majority of the configurations.

4.3. A configurational exploration of country-level DeFi adoption drivers

We present the results for DeFi adoption in Tables 8 and 9. Table 8 shows three configurations (C1 – C3) (without the cultural factors) that lead to higher DeFi adoption in a country ($N = 101$ countries). The overall solution consistency and coverage are 0.856 and 0.628, respectively (higher than the suggested thresholds of 0.8 and 0.5 (Pappas and Woodside, 2021)), indicating that this solution leads to high levels of DeFi adoption about 86 % of the time and accounts for approximately 63 % of the instances of the outcome. Interestingly, compared with crypto adoption (Table 6), population is no longer the core condition in DeFi adoption. Instead, financial development and democracy level are the core conditions in all three configurations. Configuration C1 shows that a country that has high levels of human development, income level, financial development, democracy, and network readiness, with the absence of high population and inflation tends to have a high level of DeFi adoption, regardless of the social connectedness level. Sample countries include Ireland, Finland, Denmark, Luxembourg, Switzerland, and Sweden. Configuration C2 shows that a combination of all examined factors except social connectedness leads to higher DeFi adoption, regardless of the inflation level. Countries that belong to this group include Japan, Germany, the United States, the United Kingdom, Spain, Italy, France, Canada, and Australia. Finally, configuration C3 reveals that for a high level of DeFi adoption to occur, a country needs to have high levels of population, inflation, financial development, and democracy with the absence of social connectedness, human development, income level, and network readiness. Sample countries include India and South Africa.

Table 9 reveals the configurations with cultural factors that can lead to a high level of DeFi adoption. There are up to 9 different combinations (D1 – D9) of the five groups of factors. The overall solution consistency and coverage are 0.817 and 0.745, respectively (higher than the suggested thresholds of 0.8 and 0.5) (Pappas and Woodside, 2021), suggesting that this solution leads to high levels of DeFi adoption about 82 % of the time and accounts for approximately 75 % of the instances of

the outcome. Overall, across almost all the configurations, social factors and financial development are the central factors in a majority of configurations. Future orientation is also a core condition in 3 configurations (i.e., D2, D4, D5). Compared with the crypto adoption (Table 7), we can see the different roles of social connectedness and cultural factors in DeFi adoption. Particularly, while the absence of social connectedness is the core condition in a country's crypto adoption level, the presence of social connectedness (in combination with other factors) leads to higher DeFi adoption (despite being a peripheral condition). In DeFi adoption, future orientation appears to be more important than uncertainty avoidance. On the other hand, the opposite is true for crypto adoption. Financial development also appears to be more important in the case of DeFi adoption. While the factor is a peripheral condition in all configurations of crypto adoption, it is a core condition in five configurations of DeFi adoption.

Configurations D4 and D5 highlight the important role of cultural factors (uncertainty avoidance and future orientation). Both configurations show the presence (high level) of the two cultural factors, in combination with high levels of social connectedness, human development, income level, financial development, and network readiness (configuration D4) or high levels of all other factors except social connectedness and regardless of inflation level (configuration D5) lead to a high level of DeFi adoption. Sample countries with configuration D4 include Singapore, Switzerland, Denmark, Finland, and Ireland. Sample countries with configuration D5 include Germany, Canada, the United Kingdom, and Australia. Configuration D2 highlights the role of future orientation, that is, a country with high levels of future orientation, inflation, and population and absence of all other factors tends to adopt DeFi more, regardless of uncertainty avoidance. Sample countries include Nigeria, the Philippines, and Mexico. On the other hand, configuration D9 reveals that a combination of high levels of uncertainty avoidance, social connectedness, human development, income level, inflation, democracy, and network readiness and the absence of high population, financial development, and future orientation leads to higher DeFi adoption (e.g., Czech Republic). Without taking into account the cultural factors or when these factors are at low level, we obtain three configurations (i.e., D1, D3, D8) that are largely consistent with C2.

4.4. Additional analysis for low cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption

Although our paper aims to investigate configurations that drive high cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption in a country, to provide deeper insights into the adoption, we rerun all the fsQCA analyses for low cryptocurrency/DeFi adoption. Our necessary analysis shows no necessary factor for both low cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption (with a consistency value greater than 0.90). The sufficient analysis reveals three configurations (without cultural factors) and eight configurations (with cultural factors) that are associated with low cryptocurrency adoption. Although the number of configurations is the same as that of high cryptocurrency adoption, we observe asymmetry in the results. We also document five configurations (without cultural factors) and five configurations (with cultural factors) that are associated with low DeFi adoption, which is different from the three and nine configurations found in the case of high DeFi adoption, respectively. We present the results in the Appendix (Appendix 5, 6, 7 and 8).

5. Discussion

While previous research has identified the roles of five sets of technology adoption (TA) antecedents (i.e., social, economic, political, technological, and cultural factors), there is a distinct lack of research that examines the complex interdependent relationships among these antecedents and how such interdependency can drive the country-level adoption of new technology. In this paper, addressing this major limitation, we conduct a configurational analysis of the country-level

blockchain adoption that encompasses the adoption of cryptocurrency and decentralized finance (DeFi) and how the two blockchain adoption concepts are determined by different combinations of the five sets of factors. In the following, we discuss the combinations of the five sets of factors that translate into a high level of cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption.

There are several important ways, which have emerged from our analysis, that the social, economic, political, technological, and cultural factors are combined in driving cryptocurrency adoption. High cryptocurrency adoption can arise from the combination of high population, high inflation, low social connectedness, democracy, and uncertainty avoidance (major causal factors) in a country (B2, B5, B6, and B8, Table 7). We suggest that this pattern of results could be due to the existing belief that cryptocurrency (such as bitcoin) can be used to hedge inflation (Choi and Shin, 2022; Nakamoto, 2008). More importantly, for highly populated countries (with low connectedness) to do so, low uncertainty avoidance is a key condition noting the fact that cryptocurrency is considered a risky asset (Martin et al., 2022) and that low uncertainty avoidance suggests higher risk-taking or tolerance of unpredictability of future events (Dorfman et al., 2012; Kreiser et al., 2010).

In contrast, if a country has a high level of uncertainty avoidance (risk avoiders), with a high human development index, inflation then becomes a minor factor or doesn't even matter in crypto adoption (B3 and B4, Table 7). Such a pattern of results implies that, for highly populated countries that have low social connectedness and do not favor uncertainty (i.e., high uncertainty avoidance), human development is a core condition for high cryptocurrency adoption. In this respect, our result in part mirrors the view from early research that education is critical to address adoption uncertainty and thus enhances the chance of early technology adoption. (e.g., Wozniak, 1987). Additionally, for a high level of crypto adoption to occur, there should be high levels of GDP per capita, financial development, democracy, and network readiness, despite being minor factors (B3 and B4). Given that cryptocurrencies and blockchain technology are still in their infancy and considered risky (Grover et al., 2019; Kaur et al., 2022; Motta et al., 2020), high uncertainty avoidance countries require favorable economic conditions, human and financial development, technology, and democracy so that they are confident in adopting this emerging form of technology and digital assets.

Regarding DeFi adoption (Table 9), a combination of at least two factors among the three core factors: high human development, high population, and high financial development seems to be the dominant configurations in explaining a country's DeFi adoption. This highlights the important role of network effect and available resources that a country needs for DeFi adoption. DeFi uses blockchain technology which is based on networks to operate (Toufaily et al., 2021). Thus, a high population can drive more adoption thanks to the economies of scale and network effect (Rogers et al., 2014). However, as discussed earlier, a high population can also present a challenge of administrative and financial constraints (Stier, 2017) which may hinder the adoption of DeFi. Thus, for DeFi adoption to occur, we also need a high level of human and financial development. Our study provides evidence for such interdependency among the factors, thus offering more explanations for inconclusive findings in prior research. Interestingly, when there are high levels of human development and financial development (D4 and D8), there should be more social connectedness between a country with other countries (despite being a minor condition) for a high level of DeFi adoption to occur. This result shows when social learning occurs and accelerates the adoption of DeFi and thus contributes to revealing the potential contextual conditions of the existing link between social connectedness (and learning) and technology adoption (e.g., Beaman et al., 2021; Genius et al., 2014).

DeFi adoption is essentially different from cryptocurrency in the following major ways. First, financial development is a core factor in a majority of configurations in DeFi adoption while it is a peripheral

condition in crypto adoption. Although DeFi is argued to strongly influence the traditional financial industries through its innovative features, many business models based on DeFi are built on the current financial system (decentralized currencies, decentralized payment services, decentralized fundraising and contracting (Chen and Bellavitis, 2020)). Indeed, rather than disrupting the traditional system, organizations/individuals are assimilating DeFi into the current financial system (Zetzsche et al., 2020). Thus, a high level of financial development in a country (in combination with other factors) is an important causal factor that leads to DeFi adoption in that country. Second, while uncertainty avoidance plays an important role in crypto adoption, high future orientation is found to drive high DeFi adoption. While there has been much discussion on potential scams and regulatory issues with cryptocurrency which may cause more uncertainty and risk, DeFi has been viewed more positively with many promising potentials in the future.⁷ Thus, consistent with previous research on the link between future orientation and technology adoption (e.g., Bortolotti et al., 2015; Naor et al., 2010; Zhao et al., 2014), a society in which its people have a higher level of future orientation tends to open more to DeFi.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we examine the five categories of technology adoption predictors, namely, economic, technological, cultural, social, and political factors, and identify configurations or causal combinations of such factors that are associated with a high level of cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption across countries. We indeed observe that the five sets of factors orchestrate and come together to represent different pathways of high cryptocurrency and/or DeFi adoption. Such a result supports the view that blockchain technology adoption is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. To understand why some countries are better than others in blockchain adoption, scholars and policymakers need to pay attention to a wide range of factors and how they could work together to facilitate this new technology adoption.

For both cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption, we find that GDP per capita plays a minor role (peripheral condition), or it has to be at the low level (core condition) in all configurations. This means that low-income or developing countries are able to and, in fact, have been achieving a high adoption level in cryptocurrencies and DeFi. Such a movement might be related to the awareness that blockchain technology offers viable solutions for addressing financial exclusion/unbanked issues in these countries (Chen and Bellavitis, 2020; Lichtfous et al., 2018; Schuetz and Venkatesh, 2020). As most unbanked individuals own a mobile phone (Felsenthal and Hahn, 2018), blockchain-based mobile applications can provide them with alternative financial solutions and services (Schuetz and Venkatesh, 2020). Moreover, as emerged from our configurational analysis, for these countries to achieve or sustain a high level of blockchain adoption, and hence, financial inclusion, they will need to take into account the existing levels of human and financial development, inflation, as well as those belonging to the social, cultural, and political categories to evaluate if those factors together create a favorable condition of blockchain adoption. It should also be noted that the technological factor (network readiness) plays a minor role in both crypto and DeFi adoption. Thus, developing countries should not worry much about this factor but instead focus on, for instance, human and financial development (in the case of DeFi) to encourage more blockchain adoption. The following section will discuss relevant implications for TA research and practices.

6.1. Implications for TA research and practices

Our configurational analysis of cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption

⁷ https://www.ey.com/en_nl/consulting/how-will-decentralized-finance-shake-up-your-industry.

reveals theoretical insights for TA literature regarding the roles of the economic, technological, cultural, social, and political factors in driving country-level TA. First, when taking into account the interdependency among the five sets of factors, our analysis indicates that low level of social connectedness is a core condition in almost all configurations that are related to high cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption. The results of our analysis do not support prior TA studies that have argued for the positive association between social connectedness and technology adoption (e.g., Leister et al., 2022; Wu and Pretty, 2004). For instance, Wu and Pretty's study of 50 villages in a remote region indicated that households with more connections were more likely to have a higher level of adoption of new (farming) technology. While social connectedness has been suggested as an important individual factor leading to improved technology adoption, with the presence (or absence) of other factors in our study, low social connectedness is nevertheless required for high cryptocurrency adoption. Higgins (2019) notes that to enhance the adoption of new technology, social learning needs to be about the benefits of that technology. When the performance of the new technology is not clear to people or the information about it is incomplete, the social learning process can be weaker (Molleman et al., 2014; Munshi, 2004), which in turn may hinder technology adoption. Blockchain technology is relatively new, and thus, there is not a lot of information available about the performance of this technology. Moreover, despite many potential applications across various fields, there has also been discussion on illegal activities and environmental concerns in using cryptocurrencies (Corbet et al., 2021; Mackenzie, 2022). Such information transferred through social connections among people can impede adoption. In this respect, as emerged from our analysis, a low level of social connectedness appears to be a core condition for a high level of cryptocurrency adoption. Overall, our results encourage future research to further examine the link between social connectedness and technology adoption at the country level with a particular focus on its contextual factors or moderators that either enhance or even reverse the direction of this link.

Second, we respond to the call for examining the cultural differences in TA research (i.e., Xu et al., 2021) and offer insights into the roles of cultural values in driving country-level TA. Particularly, we find that, in several configurations, national culture (uncertainty avoidance and future orientation) emerges as the core conditions and that both the presence and absence of national culture are beneficial to enhancing cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption. Our results highlight the importance of ensuring a fit or congruence between a country's cultural values and the social, economic, political, and technological factors in predicting the country's technology adoption. For instance, there must be no inflation, a high level of economic, technology, and human development, and a high level of democracy that represent as favorable conditions for those countries having a high level of uncertainty avoidance to adopt a new form of digital assets (i.e., cryptocurrency). In this respect, our work not only adds to existing discussions regarding the impact of cultural fit and values on technology adoption (e.g., Kumar et al., 2021; Qu et al., 2011; Roth et al., 2022; Vatanasakdakul et al., 2010) but it also encourages more scholarship in capturing the degree of fit between national culture and macro-economic factors and how such a fit is associated with a country's level of technology adoption phenomena.

Third, although cryptocurrency and DeFi are largely technological transformation, we find that the technological factor (i.e., network readiness) plays a less important role in driving the country-level blockchain adoption than the other factors. This observation does not support previous TA research indicating that a high level of technology factor is among the important factors for a country's technology adoption (e.g., Bhimani et al., 2022; Huarng and Yu, 2022; Larosiliere et al., 2015). As we observe from our configurational analysis, network readiness is a peripheral (or minor) condition in all configurations leading to the adoption of cryptocurrency and DeFi. When taking into account cultural values such as uncertainty avoidance and future orientation of a country, the technological factor nevertheless remains a peripheral

condition for achieving high blockchain (i.e., cryptocurrency and DeFi) adoption. As we follow Lewellyn and Muller-Kahle (2021, p. 2045) to consider peripheral conditions to have "a reinforcing role for causal features of the core conditions", we suggest that network readiness can serve as a context that influences the impact of such core factors as population, human and financial development, and national culture on blockchain adoption. Additionally, similar to the technological factor, without considering the cultural factors, we find that income level also plays a weak role in influencing blockchain adoption. Particularly, income level (GDP per capita) represents a peripheral condition in almost all configurations (except the absence of a high-income level is a core condition in crypto adoption in a sample of 43 countries in combination with cultural factors). These results might imply the reinforcing role of a country's GDP on the impact of other core factors (e.g., population or financial development) on blockchain adoption.

Finally, by offering insights to combinations of causal factors that lead to a high adoption level of cryptocurrency and DeFi, our study provides important implications for policy makers who aim to enhance financial inclusion. Importantly, we highlight the interdependence of the social, economic, technological, cultural, and political factors in the blockchain adoption decision. A factor alone is not sufficient in enhancing crypto and/or DeFi adoption in a country. Thus, we call for a holistic approach in policy to take into consideration multiple causal factors to accelerate blockchain adoption. Our study also identifies core versus peripheral factors in driving crypto and DeFi adoption in a country. This could be helpful for regulators in prioritizing their resources.

6.2. Limitations and areas for future research

It is also important to acknowledge some limitations of our paper which can be addressed in future studies. First, as our study employs cross-sectional data, the findings may be limited in terms of generalizability. Although cryptocurrencies have been around for a while, data on cryptocurrency adoption, especially DeFi adoption, are relatively new. Cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption data on Chainalysis are only available for 2020 and 2021. Moreover, as national cultures are not likely to change in a short period of time, data on national cultures are also available on a cross-sectional basis. This has discouraged us from conducting panel data or change analysis. We call for more research in the future when there is more available data to conduct longitudinal study/change analyses for cryptocurrency/DeFi adoption. Since the adoption data from Chainalysis is only available on a yearly basis, we use annual data for our study. Most of our data is from 2021 - the most updated available data at the time we conduct our research. However, we acknowledge the innovative and fast-changing nature of cryptocurrencies and DeFi. Thus, we also call for more research that employs more up-to-date data.

Second, we acknowledge that our study does not consider the legal factor in our FsQCA analysis. While the legal environment is important in promoting or hindering the adoption of new technology or assets, the regulatory framework for the use of cryptocurrency in financial markets is still under debate (Bhimani et al., 2022). Although cryptocurrency has been around for more than 10 years, it has become more popular recently, thus there are various regulations about cryptocurrencies/defi across different countries and these regulations are continuously changing (Forbes, 2023; IMF, 2022).⁸ "The regulatory fabric is being woven, and a pattern is expected to emerge. But the worry is that the longer this takes, the more national authorities will get locked into differing regulatory frameworks" (IMF, 2022). To this extent, we call for more research on the legal aspects of cryptocurrency and DeFi adoption,

⁸ <https://www.forbes.com/advisor/investing/cryptocurrency/cryptocurrency-regulations-around-the-world/>. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/fandd/issues/2022/09/Regulating-crypto-Narain-Moretti>.

especially in the financial markets.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Linh Thi My Nguyen: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Phong Thanh Nguyen:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Daniel Cross for your professional editorial assistance, The Office for Research and Innovation, The Business School, RMIT University Vietnam for your kind support with the School of English and University Pathways (SEUP) Editorial Support Program.

Appendix 1. Country-level factors (without cultural factors) sufficient for high cryptocurrency adoption

SCI	HDI	POP	GDP	CPI	FD	DEMO	NRI	Number	Crypto adoption	Raw consist	PRI consist	SYM consist
0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	0.971	0.876	0.876
0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	7	1	0.878	0.655	0.662
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	0.927	0.653	0.663
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0.896	0.636	0.636
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	10	1	0.867	0.539	0.586
1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	7	0	0.808	0.283	0.295
1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0.828	0.25	0.255
0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	2	0	0.846	0.126	0.129
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	5	0	0.782	0.124	0.128
1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	0	0.809	0.115	0.118
1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	3	0	0.798	0.104	0.104
0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	3	0	0.747	0.104	0.104
1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	3	0	0.782	0.091	0.091
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0.761	0.085	0.085
1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	10	0	0.674	0.061	0.061

Appendix 2. Country-level factors (with cultural factors) sufficient for high cryptocurrency adoption

SCI	HDI	POP	GDP	CPI	FD	DEMO	NRI	UA	FO	number	Crypto adoption	Raw consist	PRI consist	SYM consist
0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	0.987	0.962	0.962
0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.969	0.916	0.916
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.976	0.804	0.804
0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.935	0.777	0.777
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.923	0.767	0.767
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	0.956	0.764	0.771
0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0.917	0.614	0.614
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.922	0.606	0.606
0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.846	0.598	0.598
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0.940	0.576	0.585
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.818	0.315	0.315
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0.859	0.282	0.282
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.888	0.261	0.261
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0.788	0.205	0.205
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0.852	0.172	0.172
1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0.884	0.160	0.160
1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0.819	0.135	0.136
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0.776	0.112	0.112
1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0.746	0.106	0.106
1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0.768	0.104	0.104
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0.639	0.097	0.100
1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0.790	0.093	0.093
1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	6	0	0.618	0.049	0.049

Appendix 3. Country-level factors (without cultural factors) sufficient for high DeFi adoption

SCI	HDI	POP	GDP	CPI	FD	DEMO	NRI	number	Defi adoption	Raw consist	PRI consist	SYM consist
0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	2	1	0.974	0.867	0.870
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	10	1	0.945	0.842	0.892
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	0.948	0.804	0.804
0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	0.939	0.722	0.722
1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	10	1	0.851	0.499	0.528
1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	3	0	0.862	0.397	0.399

(continued on next page)

(continued)

SCI	HDI	POP	GDP	CPI	FD	DEMO	NRI	number	Defi adoption	Raw consist	PRI consist	SYM consist
0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	3	0	0.824	0.317	0.318
1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	0	0.877	0.315	0.316
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0.743	0.312	0.312
0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	7	0	0.717	0.297	0.311
1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	3	0	0.836	0.244	0.253
1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	7	0	0.656	0.104	0.105
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	5	0	0.655	0.089	0.091
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0.657	0.083	0.083
1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0.621	0.059	0.059

Appendix 4. Country-level factors (with cultural factors) sufficient for high DeFi adoption

SCI	HDI	POP	GDP	CPI	FD	DEMO	NRI	UA	FO	number	Defi adoption	Raw consist	PRI consist	SYM consist
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	0.997	0.989	0.989
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.996	0.978	0.978
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0.989	0.939	0.939
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.958	0.870	0.870
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0.964	0.833	0.950
0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.958	0.832	0.832
1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0.958	0.794	0.794
0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	0.955	0.744	0.782
0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.942	0.725	0.725
0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0.939	0.675	0.675
1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0.978	0.667	0.667
0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.901	0.643	0.643
1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	6	1	0.822	0.544	0.578
1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0.907	0.513	0.532
0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.824	0.364	0.369
1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0.908	0.358	0.462
0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.741	0.255	0.255
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0.783	0.209	0.209
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.672	0.158	0.158
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0.838	0.134	0.134
1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0.743	0.087	0.087
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0.751	0.078	0.078
1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0.551	0.074	0.074

Appendix 5. Country-level factors (without cultural factors) sufficient for low cryptocurrency adoption

Low country-level crypto adoption			
Configuration	E1	E2	E3
Social factors			
Social connectedness	●	●	⊗
Human development	⊗	●	●
Population		⊗	⊗
Economic factors			
GDP per capita	⊗	●	●
Inflation			⊗
Financial development	⊗		●
Political factor			
Democracy	⊗	●	
Technological factor			
Network readiness	⊗	●	●

(continued on next page)

(continued)

Low country-level crypto adoption			
Configuration	E1	E2	E3
Consistency	0.873	0.967	0.975
Raw coverage	0.388	0.417	0.309
Unique coverage	0.185	0.136	0.061
Solution consistency	0.908		
Solution coverage	0.683		

Note:

●

: presence of the condition,

⊗

: absence of the condition, large circle: core condition, small circle: peripheral condition.
N = 101 countries.

Appendix 6. Country-level factors (with cultural factors) sufficient for low cryptocurrency adoption

Low country-level crypto adoption								
Configuration	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Social factors								
Social connectedness	●	●	●	⊗	●	⊗	●	●
Human development								
Human development	⊗	⊗	●	●	●	⊗	⊗	●
Population								
Population	⊗	⊗	⊗	●	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗
Economic factors								
GDP per capita	⊗		●	●	●	⊗	⊗	●
Inflation								
Inflation	●	●	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	●
Financial development								
Financial development	⊗	⊗		●	●	⊗	⊗	⊗
Political factor								
Democracy	⊗	⊗	●	●		⊗	⊗	●
Technological factor								
Network readiness		⊗	●	●	●	⊗	⊗	●
Cultural factors								
Uncertainty avoidance	⊗	●	⊗	⊗	●	⊗	●	●
Future Orientation								
Future Orientation	⊗	⊗	⊗		●	⊗	●	⊗
Consistency	0.949	0.974	0.973	0.943	0.977	0.915	0.969	0.977
Raw coverage	0.269	0.191	0.231	0.251	0.363	0.187	0.145	0.147
Unique coverage	0.057	0.007	0.042	0.068	0.167	0.018	0.011	0.008
Solution consistency	0.948							
Solution coverage	0.710							

Note:

●

: presence of the condition,

⊗

: absence of the condition, large circle: core condition, small circle: peripheral condition. *N* = 43 countries.

Appendix 7. Country-level factors (without cultural factors) sufficient for low DeFi adoption

Low country-level defi adoption					
Configuration	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5
Social factors					
Social connectedness	●		●	●	⊗
Human development	⊗	⊗	●	●	●
Population		●	⊗	⊗	⊗
Economic factors					
GDP per capita	⊗	⊗	●	●	●
Inflation				●	⊗
Financial development	⊗	⊗	⊗		●
Political factor					
Democracy	⊗	⊗	●	●	⊗
Technological factor					
Network readiness	⊗	⊗	●	●	●
Consistency	0.956	0.868	0.911	0.900	0.917
Raw coverage	0.434	0.439	0.267	0.270	0.213
Unique coverage	0.056	0.090	0.017	0.028	0.035
Solution consistency	0.855				
Solution coverage	0.686				

Note:

: presence of the condition,

: absence of the condition, large circle: core condition, small circle: peripheral condition. N = 101 countries.

Appendix 8. Country-level factors (with cultural factors) sufficient for low DeFi adoption

Low country-level defi adoption					
Configuration	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5
Social factors					
Social connectedness	⊗	⊗	●	●	●
Human development	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗
Population		●	⊗	⊗	⊗
Economic factors					
GDP per capita	⊗	⊗	⊗		⊗
Inflation	⊗		●	●	⊗
Financial development	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗
Political factor					
Democracy	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗
Technological factor					
Network readiness	⊗	⊗		⊗	⊗
Cultural factors					

(continued on next page)

(continued)

Configuration	Low country-level defi adoption				
	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5
Uncertainty avoidance	○	○	○	●	●
Future Orientation	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	●
Consistency	0.919	0.896	0.964	0.980	0.974
Raw coverage	0.264	0.291	0.288	0.203	0.154
Unique coverage	0.006	0.036	0.054	0.021	0.030
Solution consistency	0.934				
Solution coverage	0.476				

Note:

○ : presence of the condition,

⊗

● : absence of the condition, large circle: core condition, small circle: peripheral condition. N = 43countries.

References

Acemoglu, D., Antràs, P., Helpman, E., 2007. Contracts and technology adoption. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 97 (3), 916–943.

Aghion, P., Howitt, P., 1992. A model of growth through creative destruction. *Econometrica* 60 (2), 323–351. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2951599>.

Allen, D.W.E., Berg, C., Markey-Towler, B., Novak, M., Potts, J., 2020. Blockchain and the evolution of institutional technologies: implications for innovation policy. *Res. Policy* 49 (1), 103865. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.103865>.

Alnasaa, M., Gueorguiev, N., Honda, J., Imamoglu, E., Mauro, P., Primus, K., Rozhkov, D., 2022. Crypto-assets, corruption, and capital controls: cross-country correlations. *Econ. Lett.* 215, 110492 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2022.110492>.

Andoni, M., Robu, V., Flynn, D., Abram, S., Geach, D., Jenkins, D., Peacock, A., 2019. Blockchain technology in the energy sector: a systematic review of challenges and opportunities. *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.* 100, 143–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.10.014>.

Ao, Z., Horvath, G., Zhang, L., 2023. Is decentralized finance actually decentralized? A social network analysis of the Aave protocol on the Ethereum blockchain. Retrieved from. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2206.08401>.

Aslam, J., Saleem, A., Khan, N.T., Kim, Y.B., 2021. Factors influencing blockchain adoption in supply chain management practices: a study based on the oil industry. *J. Innov. Knowl.* 6 (2), 124–134.

Auer, R., Farag, M., Lewrick, U., Orazem, L., Zoss, M., 2022. Banking in the Shadow of Bitcoin? The Institutional Adoption of Cryptocurrencies. Retrieved from.

Bailey, M., Cao, R., Kuchler, T., Stroebel, J., Wong, A., 2018. Social connectedness: measurement, determinants, and effects. *J. Econ. Perspect.* 32 (3), 259–280. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.32.3.259>.

Beaman, L., BenYishay, A., Magruder, J., Mobarak, A.M., 2021. Can network theory-based targeting increase technology adoption? *Am. Econ. Rev.* 111 (6), 1918–1943. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.20200295>.

Beck, R., Müller-Bloch, C., King, J.L., 2018. Governance in the blockchain economy: a framework and research agenda. *J. Assoc. Inf. Syst.* 19 (10), 1.

Becker, G.S., 1964. *Human Capital*. Chicago. of Chicago Press.

Besley, T., Case, A., 1993. Modeling technology adoption in developing countries. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 83 (2), 396–402.

Bhimani, A., Hausken, K., Arif, S., 2022. Do national development factors affect cryptocurrency adoption? *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 181, 121739.

Borgi, H., Tawiah, V., 2022. Determinants of eXtensible business reporting language adoption: an institutional perspective. *Int. J. Account. Inf. Manag.* 30 (3), 352–371. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJAIM-11-2021-0242>.

Bortolotti, T., Boscarl, S., Danese, P., 2015. Successful lean implementation: organizational culture and soft lean practices. *Int. J. Prod. Econ.* 160, 182–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2014.10.013>.

Buchholz, K., 2021. These Are the Countries where Cryptocurrency Use Is Most Common (Paper presented at the World Economic Forum).

Buterin, V., 2014. A next-generation smart contract and decentralized application platform. *White Paper* 3 (37), 2-1.

Calantone, R.J., Griffith, D.A., Yalcinkaya, G., 2006. An empirical examination of a technology adoption model for the context of China. *J. Int. Mark.* 14 (4), 1–27.

Capatina, A., Micu, A., Micu, A.E., Bouzaabia, R., Bouzaabia, O., 2018. Country-based comparison of accommodation brands in social media: an fsQCA approach. *J. Bus. Res.* 89, 235–242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.11.017>.

Carson, B., Romanelli, G., Walsh, P., Zhumaev, A., 2018. Blockchain beyond the hype: what is the strategic business value. Retrieved from. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/blockchain-beyond-the-hype-what-is-the-strategic-business-value>.

Cervellati, M., Naghavi, A., Toubal, F., 2018. Trade liberalization, democratization, and technology adoption. *J. Econ. Growth* 23 (2), 145–173. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-018-9155-5>.

Chainalysis, 2021. The 2021 Global Crypto Adoption Index: Worldwide Adoption Jumps Over 880% With P2P Platforms Driving Cryptocurrency Usage in Emerging Markets. Retrieved from. <https://blog.chainalysis.com/reports/2021-global-crypto-adoption-index/>.

Chen, Y., 2018. Blockchain tokens and the potential democratization of entrepreneurship and innovation. *Bus. Horiz.* 61 (4), 567–575.

Chen, Y., Bellavitis, C., 2020. Blockchain disruption and decentralized finance: the rise of decentralized business models. *J. Bus. Ventur. Insights* 13, e00151.

Choi, S., Shin, J., 2022. Bitcoin: an inflation hedge but not a safe haven. *Financ. Res. Lett.* 46, 102379 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2021.102379>.

Comin, D., Hobijn, B., 2004. Cross-country technology adoption: making the theories face the facts. *J. Monet. Econ.* 51 (1), 39–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmoneco.2003.07.003>.

Comin, D., Hobijn, B., 2009. Lobbies and technology diffusion. *Rev. Econ. Stat.* 91 (2), 229–244.

Comin, D., Hobijn, B., 2010. An exploration of technology diffusion. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 100 (5), 2031–2059. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.100.5.2031>.

Comin, D., Nanda, R., 2019. Financial development and technology diffusion. *IMF Econ. Rev.* 67 (2), 395–419. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41308-019-00078-0>.

Corbet, S., Lucey, B., Urquhart, A., Yarovaya, L., 2019. Cryptocurrencies as a financial asset: a systematic analysis. *Int. Rev. Financ. Anal.* 62, 182–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2018.09.003>.

Corbet, S., Lucey, B., Yarovaya, L., 2021. Bitcoin-energy markets interrelationships - new evidence. *Resour. Policy* 70, 101916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2020.101916>.

Corrales, J., Westhoff, F., 2006. Information technology adoption and political regimes. *Int. Stud. Q.* 50 (4), 911–933. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2478.2006.00431.x>.

Dekimpe, M.G., Parker, P.M., Sarvary, M., 2000. “Globalization”: modeling technology adoption timing across countries. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 63 (1), 25–42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1625\(99\)00086-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1625(99)00086-4).

Desmet, K., Parente, S.L., 2014. Resistance to technology adoption: the rise and decline of guilds. *Rev. Econ. Dyn.* 17 (3), 437–458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.red.2013.09.005>.

Dorfman, P., Javidan, M., Hanges, P., Dastmalchian, A., House, R., 2012. GLOBE: a twenty year journey into the intriguing world of culture and leadership. *J. World Bus.* 47 (4), 504–518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2012.01.004>.

Doss, C.R., 2006. Analyzing technology adoption using microstudies: limitations, challenges, and opportunities for improvement. *Agric. Econ.* 34 (3), 207–219.

Dutta, S., Lanvin, B., 2019. *The Network Readiness Index 2019*. Portulans Institute, Washington.

Felsenthal, M., Hahn, R., 2018. Financial inclusion on the rise, but gaps remain, global fin dex database shows. Retrieved from. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2018/04/19/financial-inclusion-on-the-rise-but-gaps-remain-global-fin-dex-database-shows>.

Feyen, E.H., Kawashima, Y., Mittal, R., 2022. Crypto-Assets Activity Around the World.

Fiss, P.C., 2011. Building better causal theories: a fuzzy set approach to typologies in organization research. *Acad. Manag. J.* 54 (2), 393–420.

Forbes, 2023. Cryptocurrency regulations around the world. Retrieved from. <https://www.forbes.com/advisor/investing/cryptocurrency/cryptocurrency-regulation-s-around-the-world/>.

Foster, A.D., Rosenzweig, M.R., 2010. Microeconomics of technology adoption. *Annu. Rev. Econ.* 2 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.economics.102308.124433>.

Galang, R.M.N., 2012. Government efficiency and international technology adoption: the spread of electronic ticketing among airlines. *J. Int. Bus. Stud.* 43 (7), 631–654. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jibs.2012.20>.

- Ganotakis, P., D'Angelo, A., Konara, P., 2021. From latent to emergent entrepreneurship: the role of human capital in entrepreneurial founding teams and the effect of external knowledge spillovers for technology adoption. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 170, 120912 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120912>.
- Gao, Y., Zang, L., Roth, A., Wang, P., 2017. Does democracy cause innovation? An empirical test of the popper hypothesis. *Res. Policy* 46 (7), 1272–1283.
- Genius, M., Koundouri, P., Nauges, C., Tzouvelekas, V., 2014. Information transmission in irrigation technology adoption and diffusion: social learning, extension services, and spatial effects. *Am. J. Agric. Econ.* 96 (1), 328–344. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajae/aat054>.
- Ghosh, D., Yadav, V., Jain, R., Soni, G., 2020. Adoption of blockchain in supply chain: an analysis of influencing factors. *J. Enterp. Inf. Syst.* 33 (3), 437–456.
- Gorlacheva, E., Omelchenko, I., Drogovoz, P., Yusufova, O., Shiboldenkov, V., 2019. Impact of Socio-Cultural Factors onto the National Technology Development. Paper Presented at the Digital Transformation and Global Society, Cham, 2019//.
- Greckhamer, T., Furnari, S., Fiss, P.C., Aguilera, R.V., 2018. Studying configurations with qualitative comparative analysis: best practices in strategy and organization research. *Strateg. Organ.* 16 (4), 482–495. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476127018786487>.
- Grover, P., Kar, A.K., Janssen, M., 2019. Diffusion of blockchain technology. *J. Enterp. Inf. Manag.* 32 (5), 735–757. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-06-2018-0132>.
- Hashemi Joo, M., Nishikawa, Y., Dandapani, K., 2020. Cryptocurrency, a successful application of blockchain technology. *Manag. Financ.* 46 (6), 715–733. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-09-2018-0451>.
- Higgins, S., 2019. Financial Technology Adoption. Northwestern University: Kellogg School of Management.
- Hooks, D., Davis, Z., Agrawal, V., Li, Z., 2022. Exploring factors influencing technology adoption rate at the macro level: a predictive model. *Technol. Soc.* 68, 101826 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101826>.
- Huang, K.-H., Yu, T.H.-K., 2022. Causal complexity analysis for fintech adoption at the country level. *J. Bus. Res.* 153, 228–234.
- Hwang, Y., 2005. Investigating enterprise systems adoption: uncertainty avoidance, intrinsic motivation, and the technology acceptance model. *Eur. J. Inf. Syst.* 14 (2), 150–161. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.ejis.3000532>.
- Iansiti, M., Lakhani, K., 2017. The truth about blockchain. *Harv. Bus. Rev.* 95, 118–127.
- IMF, 2022. The right rules could provide a safe space for innovation. Retrieved from <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/fandd/issues/2022/09/Regulating-crypto-Narain-Moretti>.
- Jafari-Sadeghi, V., Garcia-Perez, A., Candeló, E., Couturier, J., 2021. Exploring the impact of digital transformation on technology entrepreneurship and technological market expansion: the role of technology readiness, exploration and exploitation. *J. Bus. Res.* 124, 100–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.11.020>.
- Jalan, A., Matkovskyy, R., Urquhart, A., Yarovaya, L., 2023. The role of interpersonal trust in cryptocurrency adoption. *J. Int. Financ. Mark. Inst. Money* 83, 101715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intfin.2022.101715>.
- Jonker, N., 2019. What drives the adoption of crypto-payments by online retailers? *Electron. Commer. Res. Appl.* 35, 100848 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2019.100848>.
- Jovanović, M., Kostić, N., Sebastian, I.M., Sedej, T., 2022. Managing a blockchain-based platform ecosystem for industry-wide adoption: the case of TradeLens. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 184, 121981 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121981>.
- Kabasakal, H., Dastmalchian, A., Karacay, G., Bayraktar, S., 2012. Leadership and culture in the MENA region: an analysis of the GLOBE project. *J. World Bus.* 47 (4), 519–529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2012.01.005>.
- Kaur, J., Kumar, S., Narkhede, B.E., Dabić, M., Rathore, A.P.S., Joshi, R., 2022. Barriers to blockchain adoption for supply chain finance: the case of Indian SMEs. *Electron. Commer. Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-022-09566-4>.
- Kiiski, S., Pohjola, M., 2002. Cross-country diffusion of the internet. *Inf. Econ. Policy* 14 (2), 297–310. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-6245\(01\)00071-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-6245(01)00071-3).
- Kim, D., Kim, S., 2021. A model for user acceptance of robot journalism: influence of positive disconfirmation and uncertainty avoidance. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 163, 120448 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120448>.
- Kliber, A., Marszałek, P., Musiałkowska, I., Świerczyńska, K., 2019. Bitcoin: safe haven, hedge or diversifier? Perception of bitcoin in the context of a country's economic situation — a stochastic volatility approach. *Phys. A: Stat. Mech. Appl.* 524, 246–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physa.2019.04.145>.
- Köhler, S., Bager, S., Pizzol, M., 2022. Sustainability standards and blockchain in agro-food supply chains: synergies and conflicts. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 185, 122094 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122094>.
- Kreiser, P.M., Marino, L.D., Dickson, P., Weaver, K.M., 2010. Cultural influences on entrepreneurial orientation: the impact of national culture on risk taking and proactiveness in SMEs. *Entrep. Theory Pract.* 34 (5), 959–984. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2010.00396.x>.
- Kumar, V., Nim, N., Agarwal, A., 2021. Platform-based mobile payments adoption in emerging and developed countries: role of country-level heterogeneity and network effects. *J. Int. Bus. Stud.* 52 (8), 1529–1558.
- La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., Vishny, R., 1999. The quality of government. *J. Law Econ. Organ.* 15 (1), 222–279.
- Langenohl, A., 2022. Making uncertainty operable: social coordination through game theory in decentralized finance. *J. Cult. Econ.* 15 (5), 688–703. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17530350.2022.2085146>.
- Larosiliere, G.D., Meske, C., Carter, L.D., 2015. Determinants of Social Network Adoption: A Country-Level Analysis. Paper Presented at the 2015 48th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 5–8 Jan. 2015.
- Lee, S.-G., Trimi, S., Kim, C., 2013. The impact of cultural differences on technology adoption. *J. World Bus.* 48 (1), 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2012.06.003>.
- Leister, C.M., Zenou, Y., Zhou, J., 2022. Social connectedness and local contagion. *Rev. Econ. Stud.* 89 (1), 372–410. <https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdab022>.
- Lewellyn, K.B., Muller-Kahle, M.I., 2021. A configurational exploration of how female and male CEOs influence their compensation. *J. Manag.* 48 (7), 2031–2074. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01492063211027225>.
- Lichtfous, M., Yadav, V., Fratino, V., 2018. Can blockchain accelerate financial inclusion globally. *Deloitte Insid. Mag.* 19 (02), 1–8.
- Mackenzie, S., 2022. Criminology towards the metaverse: cryptocurrency scams, grey economy and the technosocial. *Br. J. Criminol.* 62 (6), 1537–1552. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/azab118>.
- Martin, B.A.S., Chrysochou, P., Strong, C., Wang, D., Yao, J., 2022. Dark personalities and Bitcoin®: the influence of the Dark Tetrad on cryptocurrency attitude and buying intention. *Personal. Individ. Differ.* 188, 111453 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.111453>.
- Meyer, E., Welpel, I.M., Sandner, P.G., 2021. Decentralized Finance—A Systematic Literature Review and Research Directions. Available at SSRN 4016497.
- Milner, H.V., 2006. The digital divide: the role of political institutions in technology diffusion. *Comp. Pol. Stud.* 39 (2), 176–199.
- Misangyi, V.F., Acharya, A.G., 2014. Substitutes or complements? A configurational examination of corporate governance mechanisms. *Acad. Manag. J.* 57 (6), 1681–1705. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43589326>.
- Misangyi, V.F., Greckhamer, T., Furnari, S., Fiss, P.C., Crilly, D., Aguilera, R., 2016. Embracing causal complexity: the emergence of a neo-configurational perspective. *J. Manag.* 43 (1), 255–282. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206316679252>.
- Mollema, L., van den Berg, P., Weissing, F.J., 2014. Consistent individual differences in human social learning strategies. *Nat. Commun.* 5 (1), 3570. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms4570>.
- Motta, G.A., Tekinerdogan, B., Athanasiadis, I.N., 2020. Blockchain Applications in the Agri-Food Domain: The First Wave, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbloc.2020.00006>.
- Munshi, K., 2004. Social learning in a heterogeneous population: technology diffusion in the Indian Green Revolution. *J. Dev. Econ.* 73 (1), 185–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2003.03.003>.
- Nakamoto, S., 2008. Bitcoin: a peer-to-peer electronic cash system. *Decentralized Bus. Rev.* 21260.
- Naor, M., Linderman, K., Schroeder, R., 2010. The globalization of operations in eastern and Western countries: unpacking the relationship between national and organizational culture and its impact on manufacturing performance. *J. Oper. Manag.* 28 (3), 194–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2009.11.001>.
- Pagnotta, E.S., 2022. Decentralizing money: Bitcoin prices and blockchain security. *Rev. Financ. Stud.* 35 (2), 866–907. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/haaa149>.
- Pappas, I.O., Woodside, A.G., 2021. Fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA): guidelines for research practice in information systems and marketing. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 58, 102310 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2021.102310>.
- Piñeiro-Chousa, J., López-Cabarcos, M.A., Sević, A., González-López, I., 2022. A preliminary assessment of the performance of DeFi cryptocurrencies in relation to other financial assets, volatility, and user-generated content. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 181, 121740 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121740>.
- Piñeiro-Chousa, J., Sević, A., González-López, I., 2023. Impact of social metrics in decentralized finance. *J. Bus. Res.* 158, 113673 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.113673>.
- Qin, Y., Xu, Z., Wang, X., Škare, M., 2022. Green energy adoption and its determinants: a bibliometric analysis. *Renew. Sust. Energy Rev.* 153, 111780 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111780>.
- Qu, W.G., Yang, Z., Wang, Z., 2011. Multi-level framework of open source software adoption. *J. Bus. Res.* 64 (9), 997–1003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2010.11.023>.
- Ragin, C.C., 2000. *Fuzzy-Set Social Science*. University of Chicago Press.
- Ragin, C.C., 2008a. *Set-Theoretic Versus Calibration: A Set-Theoretic Approach*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL.
- Ragin, C.C., 2008b. *Redesigning Social Inquiry: Fuzzy Sets and Beyond*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL.
- Ragin, C.C., 2014. *The Comparative Method: Moving beyond Qualitative and Quantitative Strategies*. University of California Press, Oakland, California.
- Ragin, C.C., Fiss, P.C., 2008. Net effects analysis versus configurational analysis: an empirical demonstration. In: *Redesigning Social Inquiry: Fuzzy Sets and Beyond*, 240, pp. 190–212.
- Rogers, E.M., Singhal, A., Quinlan, M.M., 2014. Diffusion of innovations. In: *An Integrated Approach to Communication Theory and Research*. Routledge, pp. 432–448.
- Roth, T., Rieger, A., Utz, M., Young, A.G., 2022. The Role of Cultural Fit in the Adoption of Fashionable IT: A Blockchain Case Study. Paper Presented at the ICIS 2022.
- Saiedi, E., Broström, A., Ruiz, F., 2021. Global drivers of cryptocurrency infrastructure adoption. *Small Bus. Econ.* 57 (1), 353–406. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00309-8>.
- Sarker, I., Datta, B., 2022. Re-designing the pension business processes for achieving technology-driven reforms through blockchain adoption: a proposed architecture. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 174, 121059 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121059>.
- Schär, F., 2021. *Decentralized Finance: On Blockchain-and Smart Contract-Based Financial Markets*. FRB of St. Louis Review.
- Schar, F., Aleksander, B., 2020. *Bitcoin, Blockchain, and Cryptoassets: A Comprehensive Introduction*. MIT Press.
- Schuetz, S., Venkatesh, V., 2020. Blockchain, adoption, and financial inclusion in India: research opportunities. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 52, 101936 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.04.009>.

- Smidt, H.J., Jokonya, O., 2022. Factors affecting digital technology adoption by small-scale farmers in agriculture value chains (AVCs) in South Africa. *Inf. Technol. Dev.* 28 (3), 558–584. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2021.1975256>.
- Sousa, A., Calçada, E., Rodrigues, P., Pinto Borges, A., 2022. Cryptocurrency adoption: a systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis. *EuroMed J. Bus.* 17 (3), 374–390. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EMJB-01-2022-0003>.
- Steers, R.M., Meyer, A.D., Sanchez-Runde, C.J., 2008. National culture and the adoption of new technologies. *J. World Bus.* 43 (3), 255–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2008.03.007>.
- Stier, S., 2017. Internet diffusion and regime type: temporal patterns in technology adoption. *Telecommun. Policy* 41 (1), 25–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.telpol.2016.10.005>.
- Svirydenka, K., 2016. Introducing a New Broad-Based Index of Financial Development. International Monetary Fund.
- Takahashi, K., Muraoka, R., Otsuka, K., 2020. Technology adoption, impact, and extension in developing countries' agriculture: a review of the recent literature. *Agric. Econ.* 51 (1), 31–45.
- Takieddine, S., Sun, J., 2015. Internet banking diffusion: a country-level analysis. *Electron. Commer. Res. Appl.* 14 (5), 361–371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2015.06.001>.
- Toufaily, E., Zalan, T., Dhaou, S.B., 2021. A framework of blockchain technology adoption: an investigation of challenges and expected value. *Inf. Manag.* 58 (3), 103444.
- Urquhart, A., Lucey, B., 2022. *Crypto and Digital Currencies—Nine Research Priorities*. Nature Publishing Group.
- van Oorschot, J.A.W.H., Hofman, E., Halman, J.I.M., 2018. A bibliometric review of the innovation adoption literature. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 134, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.04.032>.
- Varghese, G., Viswanathan, L., 2018. Normative perspectives on financial inclusion: facts beyond statistics. *J. Public Aff.* 18 (4), e1829 <https://doi.org/10.1002/pa.1829>.
- Vatanasakdakul, S., D'Ambra, J., Ramburuth, P., 2010. IT Doesn't fit! The influence of culture on B2B in Thailand. *J. Glob. Inf. Technol. Manag.* 13 (3), 10–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1097198X.2010.10856518>.
- Venkatesh, V., Davis, F.D., 2000. A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: four longitudinal field studies. *Manag. Sci.* 46 (2), 186–204.
- Vis, B., 2012. The comparative advantages of fsQCA and regression analysis for moderately large-N analyses. *Sociol. Methods Res.* 41 (1), 168–198. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049124112442142>.
- Williamson, O.E., 2000. The new institutional economics: taking stock, looking ahead. *J. Econ. Lit.* 38 (3), 595–613. Retrieved from. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2565421>.
- Wozniak, G.D., 1987. Human capital, information, and the early adoption of new technology. *J. Hum. Resour.* 22 (1), 101–112. <https://doi.org/10.2307/145869>.
- Wu, B., Pretty, J., 2004. Social connectedness in marginal rural China: the case of farmer innovation circles in Zhidan, north Shaanxi. *Agric. Hum. Values* 21 (1), 81–92. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:AHUM.0000014025.47576.72>.
- Xu, Z., Ge, Z., Wang, X., Skare, M., 2021. Bibliometric analysis of technology adoption literature published from 1997 to 2020. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 170, 120896 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120896>.
- Yadegari, M., Mohammadi, S., Masoumi, A.H., 2022. Technology adoption: an analysis of the major models and theories. *Tech. Anal. Strat. Manag.* 1–15.
- Yermack, D., 2015. Is Bitcoin a real currency? An economic appraisal. In: *Handbook of Digital Currency*. Elsevier, pp. 31–43.
- Yoon, C., 2009. The effects of national culture values on consumer acceptance of e-commerce: online shoppers in China. *Inf. Manag.* 46 (5), 294–301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2009.06.001>.
- Zetzsche, D.A., Arner, D.W., Buckley, R.P., 2020. Decentralized finance. *J. Financ. Regul.* 6 (2), 172–203. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jfr/fjaa010>.
- Zhao, F., Shen, K.N., Collier, A., 2014. Effects of national culture on e-government diffusion—a global study of 55 countries. *Inf. Manag.* 51 (8), 1005–1016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2014.06.004>.
- Zheng, Z., Xie, S., Dai, H., Chen, X., Wang, H., 2017. An Overview of Blockchain Technology: Architecture, Consensus, and Future Trends. Paper Presented at the 2017 IEEE International Congress on Big Data (BigData Congress), 25–30 June 2017.

Linh Nguyen is a Lecturer and Senior Program Manager (Finance) at RMIT University, Vietnam. She is also a CFA charterholder, regular member of CFA Institute, CFA Society Melbourne, and RMIT Fintech-Crypto Hub. Linh holds a PhD degree at QUT Business School, Queensland University of Technology, Australia. Her work has been published in journals like: *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, *Accounting and Finance*, *Finance Research Letters*. Linh also serves as an editorial board member of *Review of Behavioral Finance* journal. Her research interests include sustainable finance, behavioral finance, corporate governance, and innovation.

Phong Nguyen is a Lecturer at RMIT University, Vietnam. Phong holds a PhD degree in Management at the University of New South Wales, Australia. Phong has recently served as an Editorial Board member of the *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*. Phong's research focuses on corporate governance, blockchain-related phenomena, organizational change & crisis communication, workgroup diversity, and workplace conditions. His work has been published in journals like: *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, *Human Resource Management Review*, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, *Organizational Psychology Review*, *Journal of Business Research*. Phong is also a member of the Development Economics and Emerging Markets research cluster and FinTech-Crypto Hub at RMIT Vietnam.